

Significance of new-snow properties for snow-cover development

Costijn Zwart

July 25, 2007

Afstudeerscriptie Doctoraal Meteorologie en Fysische Oceanografie
Master thesis Meteorology and Physical Oceanography

Faculty of Science, Department of Physics and Astronomy

Supervised by:

Dr. Charles Fierz (SLF)

Dr. Roderik v.d. Wal (IMAU)

Swiss Federal Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF), Davos, Switzerland.
Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research (IMAU), Utrecht, The Netherlands.

Abstract

Thorough knowledge regarding the properties of new snow is crucial in avalanche forecasting. The input of reliable boundary conditions (e.g. density of new snow) are essential for accurate snow-cover modelling. However, the grain and bulk properties of deposited new snow have never been systematically investigated. In this contribution we present data used for verification of the snow-cover model SNOWPACK. The model, developed at the Swiss Federal Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research. (SLF), simulates the evolution of the snow cover based on meteorological input data. Its strength lies in the accurate description of crucial layers and interfaces such as surface hoar, depth hoar and melt-freeze crusts based on snow microstructure physics. The data for verification were obtained during the winter season 2005/2006 on the SLF study plot located at Weissfluhjoch, 2540 m a.s.l. near Davos, Switzerland. During snowfall events, new snow densities were measured on a half hourly to hourly basis, depending on the intensity of the snowfall. The snow crystals were characterised using various techniques such as macro photography and image processing. Specially designed sensors were placed before and during snow storms to measure the settling and temperature of different new snow layers in the snow cover. The first few days after snow storms, detailed snow profiles were taken. The fresh snow layers were then characterised with the help of high-resolution resistance measurements (SnowMicropen), snow grain characterisation, stability tests and density profiles. Based on these measurements we derived a new parametrisation for new snow density and show how this may improve snow-cover simulations. The new parametrisation improves the total snow water equivalent predictions for different seasons as well as the modelled snow-cover layering. With the corrected initial conditions, the settling of 60 cm of new snow in March 2006 was reasonably well modelled. Nevertheless, a better understanding of new snow viscosity is needed to further improve the modelled settling curves and possible causes of errors are qualitatively analysed.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Model	6
2.1	Snowpack modelling	7
2.1.1	Governing differential equations	8
2.1.2	Initial and boundary conditions	9
2.1.3	Microstructure	10
3	Field campaign	12
3.1	New snow density	12
3.2	Macro photos	13
3.3	Iso-octane	14
3.4	Snow harps	14
3.5	Profiles	15
3.6	Meteorological parameters	16
3.7	Additional measurements	17
4	Microstructure	19
4.1	Microstructure parameters	19
4.2	Dependency on meteorological conditions	20
5	New snow density	23
5.1	Dataset 05/06	23
5.1.1	Measurements	23
5.1.2	Statistical analysis	28
5.1.3	Physical justification of splitting of the temperature range	37
5.2	Older data sets	37
5.2.1	Comparison of the old and new density models	38
5.3	Density and SMP measurements	46
6	SNOWPACK simulations	50
6.1	Implementation of the new density model in SNOWPACK	50
6.1.1	Comparison with profiles 2005/2006	50
6.2	Settling	55
7	Summary	66
7.1	New snow microstructure	66
7.2	New snow density	66
7.3	Measured profiles	67
7.4	Snowpack simulations	68
A	NIR and Diethylphtalate samples	69

<i>CONTENTS</i>	2
B Statistical techniques	71
C Used meteo instruments	73
References	75

Chapter 1

Introduction

Avalanche forecasting is important for the use of high alpine areas. The increasing number of winter tourists and use of infrastructure requires a detailed and reliable avalanche forecast. The Swiss avalanche warning centre provides a national avalanche bulletin issued in the evening that is valid for the next day and a regional bulletin that is issued in the morning. The forecast relies on adequate knowledge of the snowpack and weather throughout Switzerland. This information is obtained by observers and automatic weather stations (AWS). The AWS are typically located at avalanche starting zones between 2000 and 3000 m. Air temperature, wind speed and direction and short- and longwave radiation are measured. Furthermore snow depth, snow surface and in-snow temperatures are measured.

However, the AWS cannot measure important parameters such as surface hoar, settling rates and internal structure of the snowpack. These parameters play a large role in avalanche activity. In addition, observations made by the observers are often not representative of the avalanche starting zones. For this reason, a model called SNOWPACK (see Bartelt and Lehning, 2002) and (Lehning et al., 2002a,b) has been developed by the Swiss Avalanche Warning Service (SLF) which allows sparse data and observations to be extended over a larger area. The model is driven by half hourly input from the AWS and gives avalanche forecasters additional information about the snowpack on location, where direct measurements are not available. The strength of the model lies in its description of the snow cover layering and snow microstructure. In the model, crucial layers and interfaces such as surface hoar, depth hoar and ice lenses are modelled. The model requires new-snow density and crystal shape as initial conditions. In Figure 1.1 an example is given of model output, modelled crystal types are shown. The different colours in Figure 1.1 represent the different crystal types. Bright green is new-snow and dark blue is depth hoar for example. An overview of the snow symbols used in SNOWPACK are shown in Figure 2.3. The warning signs in Figure 1.1 indicate a layer of depth hoar, snowed in surface hoar and meltforms respectively. The presence and depth of weak layers as depth- and surface hoar gives an indication for the stability of the snowpack. When such a weak layer is close enough to the snow surface, a skier can break through the layer and produce an initial failure. If this initial failure propagates through the weak layer, a slab avalanche is triggered and the slab above the weak layer slides down. In spring, water enters the snowpack. Layer boundaries are weakened, this causes wet snow avalanches. As shown in Figure 1.1, modelling the internal structure can be a great help for avalanche forecasters. In Chapter 2 an introduction to the model is given.

The input of reliable boundary conditions (e.g new-snow density, crystal shape and size) is essential for accurate snow cover modeling. Several studies have investigated new-snow densities and new-snow crystal shapes and sizes. Gold and Power (1954) related crystal shapes and sizes observed on the ground to an estimated cloud base temperature. Bossolasco (1954) investigated snowfall events on Weissfluhjoch, Davos, Switzerland. He observed a general parabolic relation between new-snow density and air temperature. Diamond and Lowry (1954) tried to relate 500-mb and 700-mb level temperatures as well as local temperatures to new-snow density. They found a somewhat linear relationship between new-snow density and 700-mb/surface temperatures. Furthermore, local measurements were also used in Meister (1985) and McGurk et al. (1988). Meister (1985) found weak relationships between new-snow density and local air temperature. McGurk et al. (1988) conducted a regression analysis which showed that local measurements were insignificant. Other studies investigated elevational and spatial controls on new-snow density (Grant

Figure 1.1: Modelled crystal types. The colours represent different crystal types. Bright green is new-snow and dark blue is depth hoar for example. The warning signs indicate potential dangerous layers such as depth hoar, snowed in surface hoar and melt forms respectively.

and Rhea (1974), Judson and Doesken (2000), Wetzel et al. (2004)). Roebber et al. (2002) diagnosed new-snow density by making use of radiosonde data and local measurements. Kajikawa et al. (2006) found that new-snow density has a strong correlation with precipitation intensity. However, precipitation intensity is not measured by the measurement stations and therefore cannot be used as input for the model. Except for Wetzel et al. (2004) all mentioned studies used daily new-snow density measurements. These measurements were conducted in the morning or with an interval 6 hours (Roebber et al., 2002). Therefore, scattering was strong when attempts were made to relate new-snow density to local measurements. In case of temperature changes, considerable metamorphism of deposited snow may take place. Densities have been found to increase from 45 to 230 kg m⁻³ within a 24 hour period (see Gray et al. 1979, 1979). If for example a snowfall event stops at 12:00 and the density is measured 09:00 the next day, large errors may occur. Wetzel et al. (2004) conducted measurements during snowfall events and found a linear relation between new-snow density and air temperature. This relation explained 52 % of the variance for that dataset. However, for our purpose, a higher time resolution is needed since our model is driven by half hourly averaged values from the AWS. Therefore, to build robust parametrisations for these initial properties, a measurement campaign was undertaken in winter season 2005/2006 on the SLF study plot located at Weissflujoch, 2540 m a.s.l near Davos, Switzerland.

The field campaign is described in detail in Chapter 3. During snowfall events specially designed sensors were used to measure temperature and settling of different new-snow layers in the snow cover. In addition, new-snow densities were measured on a half hourly or hourly basis, depending on the intensity of the snowfall. Furthermore, the crystals were characterised using various techniques such as macro photos and image processing to determine shape parameters such as dendricity and sphericity. Based on these measurements, a new parametrisation for new-snow density was derived and crystal shapes were qualitatively analysed. (see Chapters 4 and 5)

To examine the settling process in detail and verify the model, detailed snow profiles were made, the first few days after snow storms,. The fresh snow layers were then characterised with the help of high-resolution resistance measurements (SnowMicroPen), snow grain characterisation, stability tests and density profiles.

Chapter 6 describes the snowcover modelling results with the new parametrisation for new-snow density and a case study is simulated of a 60 cm snowfall event in March 2006. The results show that with the correct initial conditions, the settling curves can be modelled reasonably well.

Figure 1.2: Study plot of the SLF located at Weissflujoch, 2540 m a.s.l near Davos, Switzerland.

Chapter 2

Model

There are a large number of snow cover models. Simplified parametrisations in general circulation models, snow melt models used in hydrology and detailed snow models used in avalanche forecasting or research in snow physics. At present, a Snow Model Inter Comparison Project (SnowMIP) is running to identify the processes that are important for each application and make a comparison between the different models. In the different models involved in this project, three are detailed multi layered snowcover models, CROCUS; (Brun et al., 1989, 1992), SNTERM; (Jordan, 1991) and SNOWPACK; (Bartelt and Lehning, 2002), Lehning et al. (2002a,b). In this project, the model SNOWPACK is used, more detailed information on the other models can be found in the literature.

SNOWPACK is a one-dimensional snow cover model that was primarily developed for the support of avalanche warning in Switzerland. The model provides avalanche forecasters with supplementary information in cases where digging snowpits is impossible (due to bad weather), too time-consuming or simply too dangerous. The model is also used for other applications such as permafrost investigations (Lütschg et al., 2003), the assessment of snow-vegetation interactions, climate research (Rasmus et al., 2003), mass- and energy balance calculations for Arctic areas (Meirolid-Mautner and Lehning, 2003) and calculations of chemical solute transport in snow.

This diploma thesis focuses on aspects of layered snowpack modelling. Bartelt and Lehning (2002) and Lehning et al. (2002a,b) describe the set up of SNOWPACK in detail. To give the reader an introduction to SNOWPACK, a short summary of these papers is given in this Chapter.

SNOWPACK numerically solves the partial differential equations governing the mass, energy and momentum conservation within the snowpack using the a element method. The model has been constructed to deal with some typical features of avalanche warning, as listed below.

(1) Most avalanches occur during or after periods of intense snowfall, hence special numerical procedures have been introduced to treat new snowfall. These procedures add elements to the existing snowpack mesh. To model drifting snow, finite elements can also be subtracted from the existing finite element grid.

(2) The rate of snowpack settling gives insight into the mechanical stability of the snowpack. In order to determine the densification rate, snow is treated as a viscoelastic material capable of undergoing large non stationary deformations. The kinematic description allows for large irreversible, volumetric strains.

(3) The model is driven by half hourly averaged input from the weather stations. As soon as new meteorological data is available, the calculations can be continued while the data from the previous calculations is stored. This allows avalanche forecasters to quickly see the development of the snowpack of the last few hours.

(4) Avalanche forecasters are interested in the layering of the snowpack. Layers are defined by their size as well as their macroscopic and microscopic properties. Macroscopic properties include bulk density, mean stress, water content or temperature. Microscopic properties include ice grain size and shape, bond size or coordination number. Sharp layer discontinuities exist. Forecasters want to know the location of thin weak layers. For this reason SNOWPACK tracks the micro-structural properties of the ice lattice over time using

metamorphism routines which deal with the various temperature distributions. In order to track snowpack layers, the numerical model must employ a deforming coordinate system, a so-called "Lagrangian" formulation.

(5) The quantitative influence of solar radiation or strong warm winds (Föhn) on the stability of the snowpack is difficult to predict due to the complex energy exchange on the snowpack surface. Determining surface melting and the transport of melt water through the snowcover is essential for predicting the release of wet snow avalanches. Melt water refreezes to form thin ice layers. In SNOWPACK, all phase changes are mass and energy conserving. Since snow is modelled as a three-component (ice, water and water vapour) porous material, phase changes between the ice and water phases as well as phase changes between the ice and vapour phases are accounted for.

(6) Mass can be removed from the snowpack by wind erosion, melt water run off or water vapour sublimation. Since avalanche formation is strongly related to drifting snow, the physical treatment of mass erosion and deposition at the snowpack surface is necessary. From a numerical standpoint, this means removing finite elements from the surface, based on some erosion criteria. Snow ablation is also predicted in SNOWPACK by removing surface elements that contain only water (the ice phase has completely melted). The water flows downward, heating the snowpack; that is, refreezing on the subzero ice lattice. In an isothermal snowpack, water reaches the bottom and exits the snowcover.

2.1 Snowpack modelling

Figure 2.1 shows a multi layered snowpack and the processes that are modelled (Bartelt and Lehning, 2002). In the one-dimensional model, z is the coordinate perpendicular to a slope with angle ϕ ; $z = 0$ defines the snowpack base and $z = HS$ the snowpack surface. Assuming that all slope-parallel velocities are zero. In addition, all lateral gradients are zero. Each snow layer is described using three constituents; ice (θ_i), water (θ_w) and moist air (θ_a).

Figure 2.1: Important physical processes in snowpack modelling. (Bartelt and Lehning, 2002)

2.1.1 Governing differential equations

Bulk temperature

It is assumed that the energy exchange between the snow constituents occurs at a much faster rate than the meteorological energy exchange at the snowpack surface. This leads to a common temperature T_s (bulk temperature) for the three constituents. The meteorological boundary conditions are defined as bulk energy exchanges at the snowpack surface. It would be difficult to define the energy exchanges for each constituent phase as these are difficult if not impossible to verify experimentally (especially in the field). The conservation of energy leads to the following bulk energy equation:

$$\rho_s(z, t)c_s(\theta, z, t)\frac{\partial T_s(z, t)}{\partial t} - k_e(\theta, z, t)\frac{\partial^2 T_s(z, t)}{\partial z^2} = Q_{pc}(z, t) + Q_{sw}(z, t), \quad (2.1)$$

where ρ_s is the snow density and c_s is the specific heat capacity of snow at constant pressure,

$$\rho_s c_s = \rho_i c_i \theta_i + \rho_w c_w \theta_w + \rho_a c_a \theta_a, \quad (2.2)$$

k_e is the bulk conductivity. The terms on the right hand side of equation 2.1 are: Q_{pc} , an energy sink or source term accounting for melting and meltwater refreezing and Q_{sw} the shortwave radiation energy source term.

Vapour diffusion and water transport

The choice of the coordinate system (Lagrangian) automatically fulfils the mass conservation for the ice phase (by the ice-phase momentum equation). Only two mass conservation equations are necessary, for the air- respectively water phase.

The pore air is modelled as

$$\theta_a = 1 - \theta_i - \theta_w \quad (2.3)$$

The water phase mass (volume) conservation equation is

$$\frac{\partial \theta_w}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial J_w}{\partial z} = M_{pc}, \quad (2.4)$$

where J_w is the rate of water flow per unit area and M_{pc} is a phase change sink or source term (per unit volume) arising from meltwater refreezing or subsurface melting. The gradient in water flow is defined as

$$\frac{\partial J_w}{\partial z} = 0 \quad \text{for } \theta_w \leq \theta_r, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial J_w}{\partial z} = \dot{\theta}_f \quad \text{for } \theta_w > \theta_r, \quad (2.6)$$

where

$$\dot{\theta}_f = \frac{\partial(\theta_w - \theta_r)}{\partial t}, \quad (2.7)$$

where θ_r is the residual water content; that is, below this volumetric content, free water remains fixed within the ice matrix. Above this value, the excess water is transported immediately to the adjoining layer at rate $\dot{\theta}_f$.

Settlement equation (momentum conservation of ice phase)

The settlement equation is:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_s(z, t)}{\partial z} + \rho_s(z, t)g \cos \phi = 0, \quad (2.8)$$

where σ_s is the stress normal to the slope, g is the gravitational acceleration and ϕ is the slope angle. In the case of a flat field simulation the stress in layer l in an n layer snowpack is given by

$$\sigma_s(z) = \sum_{j=l+1}^n \rho_j g (z_j - z_{j-1}), \quad (2.9)$$

where ρ_l is the density of layer l . Snow is in a continual state of deformation. While the state of stress is known, the rate of deformation and the total state of strain are unknown. The deformations are both large and non stationary. A simple rheological Maxwell law relates the viscous strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_v$ to the mean stress,

$$\dot{\epsilon}_v = \frac{\sigma_s}{\eta_s}, \quad (2.10)$$

where η_s is the snow viscosity which is a function of σ_s . We see that large values of the snow viscosity will result in low settling rates and low values of the snow viscosity with high settling rates. Once the snow viscosity is known, densification and settling can be determined. Details on the description of the viscosity can be found in Lehning et al. (2002b).

2.1.2 Initial and boundary conditions

In SNOWPACK, 'initial' implies the specification of new snowfall mass that occurs within some time interval Δt , beginning at time t_n . The density of new-snow is parametrized based on the prevailing meteorological conditions. The mass is expressed in terms of new snowfall height Δh_n , and new-snow density, ρ_n . The existing height of the snowpack, HS, is then updated. The new snowfall height is discretized into finite elements, which are added to the existing finite-element grid. Knowing the density, the volumetric contents of the new-snow can be determined. The initial temperature of the new-snow is

$$T(t_n, z) = T_a \quad \text{for} \quad \text{HS} \leq z \leq \text{HS} + \Delta h_n. \quad (2.11)$$

T_n is the air temperature which can change during the course of a snowfall. The initial vapour pressure is

$$p_a(t_n, z) = p_s(T_a) \quad \text{for} \quad h \leq z \leq \text{HS} + \Delta h_n, \quad (2.12)$$

where p_s is the saturation vapour pressure. Over the snowfall time interval Δt , new-snow falls in an undeformed state,

$$U_i(t_n, z) = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad h \leq z \leq h + \Delta h_n. \quad (2.13)$$

U_i represents the displacement of the ice matrix. The initial strains are all zero. Because new snowfall periods usually last longer than Δt , new-snow mass is introduced to the system over many time intervals. Deformations in the underlying layers therefore begin instantaneously.

The microstructure of snow plays an important role in determining the global properties of snow. This includes optical properties (albedo, extinction coefficient), mechanical properties (viscosity, Young's modulus, strength) and physical properties (thermal conductivity, diffusivity, dielectric constant). These properties vary with the density of snow. However, at any given density, they can vary by as much as an order of magnitude due to differences in the material microstructure. The microstructure of new-snow also needs to be set. More details about microstructure can be found in section 2.1.3.

The most important boundary condition is the energy exchange on the snowpack surface. There are two possibilities in SNOWPACK. The first is the usual Neumann boundary condition,

$$k_s \frac{\partial T_s(z = h, t)}{\partial z} = q_{lw} + q_{sh} + q_{lh} + q_{rr}, \quad (2.14)$$

where q_{lw} is the net long-wave radiation energy, q_{sh} is the sensible heat exchange, q_{lh} is the latent heat exchange and q_{rr} is the heat flux from rain. A heat exchange is positive when energy is put into the snowpack, negative when energy is withdrawn.

The automatic weather stations measure the surface temperature, T_{ss} directly. Therefore, the second possibility is to specify the Dirichlet boundary condition directly:

$$T_s(z = h, t) = T_{ss}(t). \quad (2.15)$$

The Dirichlet boundary condition cannot be used during ablation periods, since the temperature at the snowpack surface is then always 0 °C. Specifying the Dirichlet condition in this case would underestimate

the true energy exchange. Therefore, when the surface temperature is well below melting temperature, the Dirichlet condition is used. When the surface temperature approaches the melting temperature the Neumann condition is used. At the ground interface, an additional Dirichlet condition is specified:

$$T(z = 0, t) = T_g(t), \quad (2.16)$$

where T_g is the measured ground temperature.

The only constraint placed on the settlement equation is that the displacement at the snowpack base is zero:

$$U_i(z = 0, t) = 0. \quad (2.17)$$

2.1.3 Microstructure

SNOWPACK uses four primary microstructure parameters: sphericity, dendricity, grain size and bond size. Details about dendricity and sphericity can be found in Chapter 4. In Figure 2.2 it is shown what is meant by bond size. Another important property is the three-dimensional coordination number, which is currently a parametrized parameter. This is the number of bonds per grain which determines the interconnectivity of the ice matrix. The consideration of bond size is novel in snowpack modelling. Bond or neck size crucially

Figure 2.2: (a) Surface section image of well-bonded snow . The necks are outlined as the grey areas. (b) Assumed model geometry for bonds and necks (Lehning et al., 2002b)

influences the mechanical properties of snow. Necks are the constricted regions connecting the ice grains. The neck geometry can be defined a number of ways. The neck connects the two grains. The bond radius r_b is defined to be the minimum constriction in the neck, and the neck length l is the length of the neck along the neck axis as shown in Figure 2.2(b).

The neck is a critical factor in determining many of the physical and mechanical properties of snow. Stresses within the snow reach peak values within the necks, since they transfer all loads between the ice grains.

Further details regarding snow metamorphism can be found in Lehning et al. (2002b). The development of dendricity and sphericity will be briefly discussed here.

Grain shape development

The formulations for the sphericity (sp) and dendricity (dd) are based on the French model formulation Brun et al. (1989, 1992). new-snow is assumed to have a dendricity of 1 and an sphericity of 0.5. In new-snow the main process is the "loss" of dendricity. Figure 2.3 shows the classification scheme to translate the microstructure parameters in conventional grain types. new-snow can either develop into faceted or

rounded snow, thereby loosing its dendricity and gaining sphericity. The rate of change in dendricity depends on the temperature gradient.

Figure 2.3: Grain classification scheme to translate the microstructure parameters in conventional grain types

Chapter 3

Field campaign

The field campaign was located on the study field of the SLF in Davos, called 'Versuchsfeld' at 2540 m above sea level. Snow profiles and a variety of measurements have been conducted here since 1936. Because there are several sensors installed at different positions within the Versuchsfeld, there is a redundancy in the measurements. The combination of the instrumental infrastructure and its accessibility makes the 'Versuchsfeld' a very suitable location for this project.

The field campaign in season 05/06 was conducted as follows:

- Before a snowfall, reference boards and snow harps¹ were positioned on the snow surface.
- During snowfall, the density of the upper 3 centimetres of new snow was measured and the crystals were characterised by eye and macro photos. Crystal shape parameters can be retrieved from the images at a later stage by image processing. Crystals were collected in a specific way (explained in section 3.3) at night or when meteorological conditions did not allow for in-situ photography.
- After snowfall, snow profiles were made at regular intervals within a few days. The settling and snow metamorphism was followed with a relatively high time resolution.

In this project several measurement techniques were used. Some techniques have already been used for many years in snow science, for example, grain characterisation by eye, compression tests (Jamieson, 1997), and hardness measurements by hand (Colbeck et al., 1991). Other techniques are relatively new, especially NearInfraRed (NIR) photography (Matzl and Schneebeli, 2002) and SnowMicroPen (SMP) measurements (Schneebeli et al., 1999). These new techniques have the advantage of allowing for more objective information to be obtained. In this Chapter, a short description of all the measurements techniques will be given.

3.1 New snow density

As often as possible, the new snow density of every snowfall was measured. This was done using a small scoop, dimensions $6 \times 5.5 \times 3$ cm. During very intense snowfall, the maximum precipitation rate is approximately 6 cm per hour. The highest time resolution of the density measurements was therefore 30 minutes. In order to measure only the first 3 cm of new snow, the frequency of measurements was adapted to the intensity of the snowfall. For less intense snowfalls, this resulted in fewer measurements.

To reduce measurement error, two identical scoops were used and 2 samples were taken with each scoop. This gave four density measurements for each time step. The mean of those four measurements was taken, giving the final new snow density. This is therefore directly related to the meteorological conditions at that time.

¹Description of the snow harps can be found in section 3.4

The weighing that was used is a very sensitive instrument and can be easily disturbed by wind for example. Although the measurements were made inside, the fluctuation is ± 0.1 gram. This gives a measurement error of approximately 1-4 %, depending on the value of the measured density. From the samples that were used for the density measurements, subsamples were also taken to analyse the crystals. Snow was taken preferably from the inside of the sample where there was no contact with the scoop therefore minimising any modification of the crystals.

3.2 Macro photos

Besides characterisation by eye, macro photos were taken to determine the initial shape of the crystals. The initial shape is an input parameter for SNOWPACK. From the density samples, a small amount of snow was taken and put on a glass plate. The crystals were then separated with help of a microscope (Nikon 30 \times). To separate the crystals, some practice is required. A needle was taped onto a plastic base of a ballpoint pen and gloves were worn to reduce heat conduction to the needle. When the crystals had been separated correctly, the glass was placed underneath the camera and a picture was taken. The ring flash was positioned in such a way that the glass plate was exactly in the middle of the ring. The ring itself was held approximately 3 cm above the surface of the desk where the tripod was placed. Figure 3.1 shows the set up for the camera. The camera used was an analogue Nikon F50 with a 105 mm macro lens, the settings

Figure 3.1: Set up of camera. The ring flash is mounted underneath the position of the glass plate. The self timer option was used to reduce disturbance.

were:

- Camera: F32
- Lens: 32, 1:1
- Flash: 1/16, DIN=27, ISO/ASA=400

- Film: Kodak elite*200 diafilm

In order to achieve the right illumination, different methods were experimented with. As an example, a construction with a styrofoam box that should give evenly spread diffuse light. In the end, the best results were obtained by using a ring flash mounted underneath the stage. The self-timer option was used to obtain the sharpest possible image. The pictures show a black background and a bright crystal, this makes the process of outlining the crystal more precise. Clearly, the hut where the samples were processed was always well below 0 °C. In spring when the air temperature was closer to 0 °C, in-situ processing was not always possible and samples had to be put in iso-octane and placed in the freezer. After developing the films, the diafilms were manually scanned and thus prepared for analysis using outlining software. An example is shown in Figure 3.2(g).

3.3 Iso-octane

As mentioned above, the conditions were not always suitable for in-situ processing of the samples. In order to preserve the crystal's original shape, cooled iso-octane was used. Small bottles were filled with iso-octane and stored in the freezer (Temperature <-30 °C). It is assumed that the iso-octane does not react with the crystals. At the end of the season all iso-octane samples were carefully transported to the cold laboratory of the SLF and stored until further analysis.

The iso-octane was not only used when meteorological conditions prevented processing, it was also used to retrieve information regarding the crystals when it was not possible to conduct measurements, during the night for example. When snowfall was expected during the night, a small bottle filled with iso-octane mounted on a pole, was placed in the field. Early in the morning the sample was collected and placed in the freezer. In addition, iso-octane was used when making profiles to obtain crystals from each individual layer, as taking photographs is too time consuming. These samples were transported to the SLF for processing in the cold lab if necessary. The processing of iso-octane samples is explained further below.

In order to separate the crystals, they had to be dried. This was done using different coffee filters and a brush. It must be done very carefully in order to prevent damage to the crystals. After drying, the crystals were separated under a microscope and a photograph was taken. The advantage of working with iso-octane is that is more practical to work with in the field and easier to process in the cold lab since the camera in the cold lab is digital and attached to the microscope. The disadvantage is that Iso-octane only suppresses air vapour diffusion. Grain boundary and grain surface diffusion still take place when the samples are stored at an incorrect temperature. This is particularly the case for smaller crystals. It is therefore important that the samples are stored well below -25 °C. Furthermore, the processing is quite rough and can easily damage the crystals. Once a bottle is opened in the cold lab, the crystals start to sublime, it is therefore necessary to work fast. Taking the photos directly in the field ensures that images of the original crystals are obtained.

3.4 Snow harps

A snow harp is a measurement device that was developed by SLF itself. It is an instrument used to measure the temperature and settling of the snowpack. It consists of a balsa wooden frame with a raster of wolfram wire inbetween. A photo is shown in Figure 3.2(c). The lightweight of the balsa wood prevents disturbance of the snowpack and the white paint keeps absorption of radiation to a minimum. Conventional temperature sensors absorb too much radiation and do not allow free settling of the snowpack. Before placement, a cable was welded to the harp and the resistance was measured. All the harps were calibrated at 0°C. Before an snowfall event, a new harp was placed on the snowpack between two vertical wires. The two ends of the harp were clipped onto the wires, this gives a measure for the height of both ends. The resistance of the wolfram wire -of the harp itself- gives measure for the temperature. Once the harp was snowed in, it slid down over the two wires, following the settling of the snowpack. The values for height of both ends and temperature were transmitted from the data logger to a server at the institute where it was recorded.

Placement of the harps must be done carefully and with low wind speeds. When the wind speed is high or a high wind speed is expected, small snowballs were placed on the harp to prevent it from blowing away

before it was snowed in. A video camera was aimed on the harps and an image was taken every minute during the season. In this way, the burying in the snow was followed from a distance and snowdepth and processes on the surface (wind effects, surface hoar) were re-examined afterwards. To keep the disturbance to a minimum, a ladder was used for access. In Figures 3.2(b) and 3.2(c) placement of a harp and a harp are shown respectively.

The resolution of the height of the harps is in the order of 1 mm, the resolution of the temperature measurements is in the order of 0.1°C. In some cases ice on the wires disturbed the connection between the harps and the wires. Therefore the signal of the harps required smoothing afterwards. There were no instances where that both ends of the harps (east and west side) lost connection at the same time, retrieving the correct heights was therefore not a significant issue.

3.5 Profiles

In order to follow the settling of the newly deposited snow in detail, snow profiles were made after a snowfall of more than 20 cm. Within the first ten days after snowfall, three profiles were made. Regular profiles which were made on the 15th and 30th of the month were also used for comparison. Before an expected snowfall, snowboards were placed besides the harps. The snowboards served as a reference, after the snowfall the snowboards acted as an indicator for the depth of the old snow layer. The snowboards were solid 60×60×5 cm wooden boards, painted white to minimise absorption of radiation. Different snowboards were tested, e.g thin plastic ones and metal/foam boards. However, solid wooden boards proved the most convenient considering movement by wind. When placing the snowboards, they were pressed in the snow so that the upper edge of the board was flush with the snow surface.

Once the snowfall stopped, a profile was made of the new snow layer. The profiles were always made in an undisturbed section of the study field.

SnowMicroPen measurements

SMP measurements were conducted before the profile was made. The SMP is a high-resolution penetrometer. Detailed information regarding this instrument and information which can be retrieved using the SMP can be found in Schneebeli et al. (1999). With the SMP it was possible to obtain high-resolution objective information about snow resistance and snow microstructure without having to dig a profile. The displacement resolution is better than one mm so as to detect significant changes in resistance, the force signal was measured every 0.004 mm. Along the line where the profile was made, 5 SMP measurements were made, with 50 cm inbetween. Before starting the measurements it was necessary to cool down the tip of the sensor in the snow, if the temperature of the sensor was not well below °C, the measurements would start drifting.

NearInfraRed photography

NIR photography allows for the acquisition of objective information concerning the layering of the snowpack and its micro structural parameters such as the specific surface area of the grains. After the SMP measurements, the profile was dug very carefully. The surface was smoothed with a brush or the backside of the snow saw. Reflectors were placed at the border of the area of interest and this area was shaded with a large cloth. A prepared profile is shown in Figure 3.2(i). Images were taken with a special modified camera, to be processed afterwards. During time of this field campaign, NIR photography was relatively new and it was not always clear what was the best way of obtaining optimal images. The potential of NIR is high, however for this project the lack of protocol led to poor results. The images were therefore not analysed for further use. In Appendix A, an example of a NIR photograph is given.

Manual profile

The snow profiles were made in the same way as regular profiles, however, the additional attention was given to the top most snow layer of the snowfall period. Tried was to obtain high layer resolution in the new snow layer. Hardness of the layers was measured by hand according to the standard procedure

described in Colbeck et al. (1991). The different crystals were characterised by eye making use of a magnifying glass. In spring, when a high air temperature made characterisation difficult, iso-octane was used. With an interval of 2-5 cm the temperature was measured throughout the profile. After identifying the different layers grain types and sizes, a density profile was made. The density was measured every 3 cm, with help of the same scoop and scale used during snowfall density measurements. In addition to the density profiles, the mass and height of the whole new snow layer was measured -at once- using a large cylinder and spring scale. This allows to determine the SnowWaterEquivalent (SWE) for the new snow layer.

Beside the profile, two compression tests were conducted. A compression test is a manual test used by avalanche forecasters, which gives information about the presence and location of weak layers in the snow-pack (see Jamieson, 1997). A square block of $30 \times 30 \times$ new snow depth was cut out carefully with the snow saw. The blade of a snow shovel was put on top of the block and according to a standardised sequence of taps the block was compressed. Weak layers appear as horizontal cracks in the block. Once the position of the weak layers was known, samples over the weak layers were taken with diethylphtalate.

Diethylphtalate samples

On the position where the profiles were made, samples were taken in such a way that the weak layer was positioned in the middle of the sample. A little cardboard box (part of a milk-box) was placed over the weak layer with the help of a little iron saw. The sample was carefully cut out of the snow and the box was filled with pre-cooled diethylphtalate. See Figures 3.2(j) and 3.2(k). Filling the sample must be done with great patience, if the sample is filled too quickly, air bubbles develop which ruin the sample. Filling two samples at once forces the operator switch between the samples, which gives the samples time to absorb the fluid. Freezing of the sample was enhanced with the use of dry-ice and the samples were stored in the freezer. Afterwards, the samples can be cut in the cold lab and with help of specific techniques the microstructure can be analysed. Until time of writing, the samples were not used for further analysis considering this project. In Appendix A an example of a processed sample is given

3.6 Meteorological parameters

On the MST frame, see Figure 3.2(a), several instruments were mounted which measured the following parameters:

1. Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
2. Surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
3. Relative humidity (%)
4. Wind speed (m s^{-1})
5. Snowdepth (cm)

The instrument that measured air temperature/humidity was not ventilated (Rotronic). The surface temperature was measured using IR thermometry and had a precision of approximately 1°C . The snowdepth was measured ultra sonic with an precision of approximately 1 cm.

The instruments were mounted on a frame with a minimum distance of 1.5 m above the snow surface. During the season, the height of the frame was adapted to the snowdepth. Another set of instruments close to the MST frame is the METE frame. The same measurements were conducted with the difference that the instruments were ventilated for air temperature and relative humidity (Thygan). The values for the different parameters were measured every minute and averaged over 30 minutes. For the wind speed, the average value was stored as well as the maximum value measured half hourly. Incoming/outgoing long- and short-wave radiation were measured as well. These instruments (wind: Young wind anemometer, SWin-out: Kipp & Zonen CM21 Pyranometer, LWin-out: Eppley PIR Pyrgeometer) were mounted 4.5 m above the ground

3.7 Additional measurements

In addition to the measurements mentioned above, some other measurements were made in the Versuchsfeld, which can be used to verify the measurements conducted at the MST project site.

Snowdepth, HS, in the middle of the Versuchsfeld, there is a large pole that was used to measure the official snowdepth at the Versuchsfeld throughout the winter. This was done every morning and afternoon by the Hauswart².

HN, the amount of new snow over 24 hours was also measured by the Hauswart. In addition, the snow water equivalent (**HNW**) and depth of the new snow were measured.

Rain gauge, this instrument measures the amount of precipitation. It is not very reliable in terms of amount of new snow but the time of snowfall can be reasonably well obtained with this instrument. In combination with the measurements of the Hauswart, the mass added to the snowpack can be reconstructed every half hour over the whole season. This was important for model runs.

Snowpillow, the snowpillow is a pillow situated on the ground. The pillow is filled with glycol and pressure changes within the pillow are recorded with the use of a pressure gauge. A snowfall loads snow on top of the pillow and the increase in pressure gives a measure for the mass of the new snow.

Profiles, every 15th and 30th of the month, profiles were made along the profile lines in the Versuchsfeld. In these profiles the same measurements were conducted as in the new snow profiles. Although the focus is not especially on the new snow layer as it was in the new snow profiles, the profiles can be used as comparison or addition to the new snow profiles.

²PhD. Student who has duty on Weissfluhjoch

Figure 3.2: (a) MST frame, (b) Placement of a snow harp with the help of ladder, (c) Snow harp just placed at the surface, (d) the camera, (e) density measurement, (f) analysis of crystals, (g) photo of crystals, (h) SMP measurement, (i) NIR, (j) two samples over weak layers (k) sample filled with diethylphtalate.

Chapter 4

Microstructure

Brun et al. (1992) introduced a scheme to describe the snow microstructure. The parameters used are; dendricity, sphericity and grain size¹. This scheme is shown in Figure 2.3. New snow is assumed to have a dendricity of 1. During the snow metamorphism, new snow loses its dendricity and develops into rounded or faceted crystals with dendricity 0. Sphericity is used to distinguish between rounded and faceted crystals.

The parametrisations were developed in order to make convenient comparison between the modelled snowpack and the observations in the field, and function well in this way. Painter et al. (2007) showed that there is a very poor or even no correlation between traditional grain size and optical diameter. It is therefore difficult to relate parameters like dendricity, sphericity and traditional grain size to physical properties such as albedo of the snowpack. However, for modelling of the mechanical properties of the snowpack, a parameter as optical grain size is not sufficient. And parametrisations of shape parameters are needed.

4.1 Microstructure parameters

Dendricity

Dendricity is a measure for the complexity of the shape of a crystal. It is defined as

$$dd = \frac{P^2}{4\pi A}, \quad (4.1)$$

where P is the perimeter and A the area of the crystal. The dendricity gives a good distinction between new snow crystals which tend to have highly complex shapes, and older crystals which have a more simpler shape. The values for the dendricity are mapped onto the interval [0 1], the mapping was introduced by Lesaffre et al. (1998), the dendricity is then defined over all objects of a sample:

$$\hat{dd} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N P_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N 4\pi A_i} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } dd < 2 \\ \frac{dd-2}{10} & \text{if } 2 < dd < 12 \\ 1 & \text{if } dd > 12, \end{cases}$$

where i is the object number.

Sphericity

The sphericity of a pixel is defined as

$$sp = \frac{\sigma_{\kappa^+}}{\bar{\kappa}^+}, \quad (4.2)$$

where κ^+ is the standard deviation of the positive curvature and $\bar{\kappa}^+$ is the mean positive curvature. The curvature is defined as

$$\kappa = \frac{d\phi}{ds}, \quad (4.3)$$

¹As defined in Colbeck et al. (1991)

where ϕ is the angle between the tangent to the curve and the x -axis and s is the arc-length. The sphericity indicates whether the crystal has a relatively constant curvature or that the curvature varies more and extreme points exist in the outline. The former is the case with rounded grains where the latter occurs with faceted crystals which contain flat edges and sharp corners. As with the dendricity, the sphericity is mapped on the interval $[0, 1]$ over all pixels of the objects of a sample according to Lesaffre et al. (1998):

$$\hat{sp} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } sp < 0.8 \\ 2(1 - sp) + 0.6 & \text{if } 0.8 < sp < 1.3 \\ 0 & \text{if } 1.3 < sp. \end{cases}$$

According to the parametrizations, the sphericity of a very rounded crystal should be 1 and the sphericity of a faceted crystal ought to be 0. New snow crystals should be around 0.5. However, sphericity is a suitable parameter to describe crystals of low dendricity and for new snow sphericity does not really make sense.

To give the reader insight in the different parameters, different crystals are shown in Figure 4.1, and the values for the different parameters are listed in table 4.1. Note that the different parameters are computed for individual crystals and not for the samples. The first three crystals (stellar, plate, needle) are new snow crystals, and the fourth is an older rounded crystal. The stellar has a dendricity of 0.87, what is expected for new snow. The needle and plate however have dendricities of 0 and 0.44 respectively. Although these are new snow crystals, the dendricities have values that are expected for old snow. This is what is expected from the images.

These images demonstrate that a problem rises with the definition of the model stated above. According to the grain classification diagram, Figure 2.3, new snow should always have a dendricity of 1. The plate and needle show features of a faceted crystal and will never be classified as a new snow crystal based on their dendricity. The values in table 4.1 show that dendritic crystals can be well distinguished from rounded crystals, however, problems rise when new snow crystals have shape characteristics that are similar to faceted crystals. Nevertheless, in most cases when new snow consist of dendrite shaped crystals, the dendricity gives a good indication for the shape of the crystal.

	Stellar	Plate	Needle	Rounded
dendricity	0.87	0	0.44	0
sphericity	0	0.6	0	1

Table 4.1: Values of microstructure parameters for different crystals.

4.2 Dependency on meteorological conditions

For the meteorological data, the MST station was used. Three different periods in winter and in spring were analysed. Note that the different parameters were computed per grain and not per sample, such that each star represents one object grain of the sample. The different stars in the figures represent the different grains.

In Figure 4.2(a) the wind and temperature are plotted against sphericity. Figure 4.2(a) shows that the wind does not have a large influence on the sphericity. There were a few points (indicated with an arrow) that have a relatively high sphericity, the remaining points have sphericity's in the same range, no trend is visible. The few points that have high sphericity values occurred when windspeeds were low. It may be that sharp dendrites were present in these measurements. However, while the sphericity did not show a clear relation with wind (Figure 4.2(a) and temperature (4.2(b)), the dendricity shows decreases with increasing windspeeds, see Figure 4.2(c). The minimum values remain constant over the different windspeeds. The relation between maximum dendricity and windspeed seems to be quite linear. The Dendricity does not seem to depend to a large extent on air temperature, see Figure 4.2(d). The spread is large and there is not

Figure 4.1: Different new snow crystals and one old snow crystal.

Figure 4.2: Microstructure parameters plotted against wind and temperature. The red stars represent the different grains of the samples.

a clear relation visible in Figure 4.2(d).

The results above show that especially the dendricity is dependent on meteorological conditions and that it is not correct to use an initial constant dendricity in SNOWPACK. Sensitivity studies are needed to determine what the effect of a varying initial dendricity is for SNOWPACK and if a parametrisation would bring much improvement. Due to a lack of time, the solid sensitivity studies are not performed and the dendricity is not explicitly parametrized.

Chapter 5

New snow density

The prediction of new snow density is a problem in snowfall forecasting. Forecasters often use the so-called 10-to-1 rule. The rule assumes that the depth of the snowfall is 10 times the liquid water equivalent. This implies a snow density of 100 kg m^{-3} . However, measurements show that snow density varies between 25 and 200 kg m^{-3} . Although the 10-to-1 rule is an oversimplification and several studies have pointed out that large errors are made in the estimation of snowdepth, it has been used already for more than 100 years. Historically little research has been addressed to the snow-density problem, as highlighted by Judson and Doesken (2000, sec. 1).

New snow density is affected by (a) in-cloud processes, that affect the shape and size of growing ice crystals; (b) sub cloud processes (riming, wind) that modify/compact the ice crystals when they fall; and (c) ground level compaction due to the prevailing weather conditions. Understanding how these processes affect new snow density is difficult because direct observations of cloud micro physical processes, thermodynamic profiles and surface measurements are often unavailable. Although attempts have been made by Roebber et al. (2002) in this direction, using surface and radiosonde data look promising, at the time of writing, only local measurements were available. A relationship needs to be found between new snow density and the local prevailing meteorological conditions. An empirical relation between new snow density and local meteorological conditions was found by Lehning et al. (2002a). This relationship was based on statistical analyses where air temperature, snow surface temperature, relative humidity and windspeed were the predictor variables for new snow density. The dataset used was quite limited in the range of different measured variables, especially air temperature.

In order to obtain correct predictions of new snow density over a wider data range, new snow densities were measured during the season 05/06 and an attempt has been made to improve the parametrization for new snow density. In this Chapter, the different data sets were analysed and a regression analysis was conducted to obtain a more generally valid density model.

5.1 Dataset 05/06

5.1.1 Measurements

In total, 396 density measurements were made during or within one hour after snowfall, this results in a final dataset of 99 data points. The new snow density varies greatly for the different snowfall events, with minimum values around 25 kg m^{-3} and maximum values around 200 kg m^{-3} . In Figure 5.2, the density is plotted against the different meteorological parameters that were measured.

Figure 5.2(c) shows that the minimum densities increase with increasing windspeed. Although the minimum values increase with higher windspeeds, a clear trend is not visible. While the scatter is large, the number of measurements in the high windspeed range ($> 6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) was not as large as in the lower ranges. Striking is that the highest densities were not measured with high wind speeds but in the medium ($3 - 5$

m s^{-1}) or even low range ($< 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). This is remarkable as it is more likely to see a increase in density with windspeed due to compaction.

The relative humidity plot 5.2(d) shows clear outliers, with values for the relative humidity being lower than 70%. The outliers in the humidity plot are special in a way because most measurements were in the range of 80% and 100% during snowfall.

The reason that outliers occurred in the wind and humidity measurements can be (i) technical failure or (ii) the meteorological conditions at time of measurement were not representative for the time that the snow was formed.

For relative humidity values below 70% snowfall is not expected. This is confirmed by the images of the video. The measurements were taken right after snowfall and the relative humidity was not representative for the density of the snow that was measured. Some of the windspeed outliers are shown in Figures 5.2(a) and 5.2(b). The two Figures show that there was a relatively long period of high windspeeds, the density measurement were than taken right after the drop in windspeed. This caused the outliers in Figure 5.2(c) Actually these outliers should be shifted towards the higher wind values. Another reason for the relatively high densities could be quick settling of the snow after deposition. If the time span between the snowfall stops and measurement time is long (more than one hour), the initial settling may be large. Especially when air temperatures are close to 0°C . In the case of the measurements with low air temperatures (around -10°), the initial settling will probably be quite small.

The data points that were not used in further analysis regarding windspeed were the red circles in Figure 5.2(c), the black squares in Figures 5.2(c) and 5.2(d) were data points taken when there was no snowfall at that time. In total, 22 data points were excluded, 10 due to windspeed and 12 due to low humidity. The final data set on which the analysis was conducted contained 77 data points. Excluding these data points reduced the range of the density from $22.5\text{-}205.5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ to $22.5\text{-}175 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$

Figure 5.1: Snow morphology diagram, Libbrecht (2005)

After removal of the outliers in the wind and humidity plots a trend became more visible, see Figures 5.3(a) and 5.3(b). The wind plot shows a positive trend, while the humidity plot shows a negative trend. The positive trend in the windspeed was expected due to more compaction.

The snow morphology diagram in Figure 5.1 shows that in general, the complexity of the crystal shapes increases with increasing supersaturation. In the higher humidity range, more complex shapes such as dendrites develop. With lower supersaturation values, it is more likely that plates are the dominant shapes. The more complex the shape of the crystal, the more air is in between the crystals. Plates can stick closer together as dendrites which leads to higher densities. The measurements of season 2005/2006 show a decreasing density for increasing relative humidity.

Figures 5.2(e) and 5.2(f) show that density increases with increasing temperature. Especially in lower densities (starting at 30 kg m^{-3}) there are two bands in which the densities seem to increase linearly with temperature. A large dependency of density on temperature is expected on days without wind. Therefore it was interesting to examine in which wind range the measurements laying in the two bands are taken. In Figure 5.3(c), the colour of the symbols corresponds to a windspeed shown on the right (in m s^{-1}). The lower band is dominated by blue, this represents the lower wind speeds ($1\text{-}2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). In this range, a large temperature influence is expected and although there is a lot of scatter, a positive linear relationship is clearly seen. Striking is the band above this lowest band, where there is some mixing of all the different wind regimes. This is however dominated by green-orange which corresponds to wind speeds of $4 \text{ to } 7 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Even in this higher wind speed band the density seems to depend linearly on temperature. The snow surface temperature plot (Figure 5.3(d)) shows approximately the same features, however somewhat weaker, the spread is larger. A clear linear band is not seen in the humidity plot, Figure 5.3(e). What the plot does show are two clusters, one dominated by blue in the lower density range (up to 100 kg m^{-3}) and another cluster dominated by yellow/red (above 100 kg m^{-3}). Figure 5.3(f) shows the different points in time in which the measurements were taken. The different colours represent different points in time. The plot shows that the general trend seen in Figure 5.3 are not only appearing during the short measurement periods, but that they are general trends appearing over all the data points.

Figure 5.2: Density measurements (blue stars) with outliers, red circles represent outliers due to non-representative windspeeds, black squares represent data points when it was not actually snowing. Wind effect in two different periods (a and b), density against windspeed (c), density against relative humidity (d), density against air temperature (e) and density against snow surface temperature (f).

Figure 5.3: Final data set without outliers. Temperature against windspeed (a), density against relative humidity (b), blue stars represent data points. Density against air temperature and wind (c), density against snow surface temperature and wind (d), density against relative humidity and wind (e), the circles represent the data points, the colour corresponds to the windspeed scale shown at the right of the Figures. Density against air temperature and date (f), the circles represent the data points, the colour corresponds the the date number shown in the right of the Figure.

5.1.2 Statistical analysis

Regression analysis data set 05/06

A description of the statistical techniques that were used can be found in Appendix B. The semi-quantitative analysis conducted in the previous section gave rise to the following terms being taken into account as predictor variables in the regression analysis: air temperature (T_a), snow surface temperature (T_{ss}), relative humidity (RH) and windspeed (VW). Although the Figures 5.3(c) and 5.3(d) from the previous section were quite similar, the snow surface temperature was taken into account because it may be an important term in certain situations. For example in the case when the air temperature is well above 0 °C and the snow surface temperature at 0 °C, the snow surface temperature might then have a large influence on the new snow density. The correlation between the new snow density and the chose predictor variables is shown in table 5.1. The density was relatively strongly correlated with windspeed and relative humidity. A corre-

	ρ	T_a	T_{ss}	RH	VW
ρ	1.0000000				
T_a	0.1698395	1.0000000			
T_{ss}	0.1566381	0.9209961	1.0000000		
RH	-0.4737803	-0.1130873	-0.06712748	1.0000000	
VW	0.5466890	-0.2184363	-0.15145190	-0.45565283	1.0000000

Table 5.1: Correlation coefficients of density and meteorological parameters, dataset 05/06.

lation between density with either air temperature or snow surface temperature was weak due to the large scatter seen in Figures 5.2(e) and 5.2(f). Windspeed and relative humidity were relatively strongly negatively correlated, this might be caused by atmospheric mixing effects or stronger ventilation of the sensor by higher windspeeds. The surface temperature and air temperature showed a very strong correlation of 0.92. The measurements were made during snowfall, the long wave radiation is then trapped by the clouds and radiated back to the surface. The difference between air temperature and snow surface temperature was therefore very small at time of measurement. (< 1 °C)

The first step in the regression analysis was to perform a regression with the terms stated above. The residuals are shown in Figures 5.4 and 5.5 and the coefficients in table 5.2. The values representing collinearity between the variables (R^2_x value) indicated that there was a relatively high collinearity between the air and surface temperature. This is what was expected from the correlation coefficients in table 5.1. When a significance level of 5 % (p.value of 0.05) is assumed, the surface temperature term did not seem to be significant, the p.value is 0.6199. The air temperature was also above this level, however this was due to the presence of the surface temperature. The sign of the coefficients was as expected from the plots in Section 5.1.1: positive for the surface temperature, air temperature and windspeed and negative for relative humidity.

An important assumption in regression analysis is that the errors are distributed normally and that they all have the same variance. In the case of density, the error is a percentage of the measured value. Increasing densities will thus lead to an increase in error. Figure 5.5 shows that the scattering of the residuals is increasing with increasing values of the windspeed. In order to achieve a variance that was normally distributed, transformations were necessary. For data types as fractions (density), percentages (humidity), standard transformations should always be used (see Stahel (2006)). The residual plots for the air temperature and snow surface temperature did not gave an immediate reason for transformations. The following "first aid" transformations were applied: ¹:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho &\Rightarrow \text{Log}_{10}(\rho) \\ \text{VW} &\Rightarrow \text{Log}_{10}(\text{VW}) \\ \text{RH} &\Rightarrow \arcsin(\sqrt{\text{RH}/100})\end{aligned}$$

¹Named so by J.W.Tukey

After applying the transformations and leaving out the snow surface temperature, the overall R^2 value increased from 0.39 to 0.44. The residual plots are shown in Figures 5.6 and 5.7 and the numeric results are listed in table 5.3. In the lower range of the fitted values in Figure 5.6 the absolute value off the residuals was much larger than the values in the higher range, while the second plot in Figure 5.7 shows a decreasing trend. Taking a closer look on the residuals-temperature plot, seen is that for temperatures below approximately -14°C the error strongly increases. In Figure 5.3(c) in section 5.1.1 there was a small cluster of points with relatively high densities for temperatures below -14°C . Splitting the analysis in two temperature regimes, $T_a \leq -14^\circ\text{C}$ and $-14^\circ\text{C} < T_a$ gives the following model:

$$\log_{10}(\rho) = \begin{cases} \beta_0^{(1)} + \beta_1 T_a + \beta_2 \arcsin(\sqrt{\text{RH}/100}) + \beta_3 \log_{10}(\text{VW}), & \text{if } T_a < -14 \\ \beta_0^{(1)} + \beta_0^{(2)} + \beta_1 T_a + \beta_2 \arcsin(\sqrt{\text{RH}/100}) + \beta_3 \log_{10}(\text{VW}), & \text{if } -14 < T_a. \end{cases}$$

The numerical results are given in table 5.4 and Figures 5.8 and 5.9. The plots in Figures 5.8 and 5.9 show that the smooth comes quite close to the green reference line and falls reasonably in the range of the simulated curves. The residuals against the windspeed plot shows that for lower windspeeds ($\text{VW} < 2 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) the residuals become larger. For the lower windspeeds, the density is mainly determined by the temperature and humidity and the influence of windspeed is negligible. This can be seen in Figures 5.3(a) and 5.3(c). In the blue band the density increases with increasing temperature. In addition low speeds occur at the higher and lower densities as well. Therefore, to retrieve a better regression for windspeed, windspeeds below 2 ms^{-1} are set to 2 ms^{-1} .

Figure 5.3(c) suggests a possible interaction term of wind and temperature. This effect was not significant as the two fits for the different wind regimes are parallel so the effect is only additive. Interaction terms are only significant when the slopes of the two trends differ. Other possible interaction terms involving air temperature, snow surface temperature, relative humidity and wind speed were examined and found not to be significant either.

The final model contains the air temperature, relative humidity and windspeed as predictors. No cross-terms are used. The temperature and windspeed are split in two regimes. This lead to an increase of the explained variance from 47% to 72%. The root mean squared error is 1.3 kg m^{-3}

	coef	stcoef	signif	R2.x	p.value
(Intercept)	174.1495816	0.0000000	1.7204451	NA	0.0010
TA	3.1199468	0.3675119	0.7572255	0.6323487	0.1355
TSS	-0.9698981	-0.1175039	-0.2498835	0.6205386	0.6199
RH	-1.0836874	-0.2051246	-0.9747979	0.1520326	0.0559
VW	7.8705152	0.5157052	2.3973174	0.1705194	0.0000
St.dev.error: 26.06 on 72 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R ² : 0.4231 Adjusted R-squared: 0.3911					
F-statistic: 13.2 on 4 and 72 d.f., p.value: 4.067e-08					

Table 5.2: Regression (I)

	coef	stcoef	signif	R2.x	p.value
(Intercept)	2.669909719	0.0000000	6.1821933	NA	0e+00
TA	0.008110176	0.1645326	0.9587252	0.01196074	6e-02
asin(sqrt(RH/100))	-0.644205339	-0.3397516	-1.8690642	0.06718680	4e-04
log10(VW)	0.215734044	0.4624181	2.5668148	0.05877888	0e+00
St.dev.error: 0.1438 on 73 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R ² : 0.4716 Adjusted R-squared: 0.4499					
F-statistic: 21.72 on 3 and 73 d.f., p.value: 3.713e-10					

Table 5.3: Regression (II)

	coef	stcoef	signif	R2.x	df	p.value
β_0^1	3.27820894	0.0000000	8.047280	NA		0
β_1	0.03132918	0.6605352	3.989635	0.2535116		0
β_2	-0.74783337	-0.4173531	-2.781108	0.1764309		0
β_3	0.30943402	0.3605771	2.338524	0.1984519		0
β_0^2	-0.35976206	-0.7175756	-4.245103	0.2688501		0
St.dev.error: 0.09879 on 71 degrees of freedom						
Multiple R ² : 0.7272 Adjusted R-squared: 0.7119						
F-statistic: 47.32 on 4 and 71 d.f., p.value: 0						

Table 5.4: Regression (III)

Figure 5.4: Residual plots (I). Residuals against fitted values (upper left), absolute standardized residuals against fitted values (upper right), QQ plot(lower left), Leverage plot(lower right).

Figure 5.5: Residual plots (I). Residuals against temperature (upper left), residuals against snow surface temperature (upper right), residuals against relative humidity (lower left), residuals against windspeed (lower right)

Oct 26, 00:25:57 |

Figure 5.6: Residual plots (II), with applied transformations. Residuals against fitted values (upper left), absolute standardized residuals against fitted values (upper right), QQ plot(lower left), Leverage plot(lower right).

Oct 26, 00:30:30 |

Figure 5.7: Residual plots (II), with applied transformations. Residuals against air temperature (upper left), residuals against relative humidity (upper right), residuals against windspeed (lower left).

Figure 5.8: Residual plots (III), with applied transformations + split temperature and wind range. Residuals against fitted values (upper left), absolute standardized residuals against fitted values (upper right), QQ plot(lower left), Leverage plot(lower right).

Figure 5.9: Residual plots (III), with applied transformations + split temperature and wind range. Residuals against air temperature (upper left), residuals against relative humidity (upper right), residuals against windspeed (lower left).

5.1.3 Physical justification of splitting of the temperature range

An important step in this regression analysis involves dividing the dataset into different temperature ranges. The question is now, if this can be done on a physical basis or if it is only an statistical approach.

In Figure 5.3(c), two wind regimes were seen in which the new snow density seems to depend linearly on air temperature. In one regime the windspeeds were low ($0-3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), and in the other regime windspeed was higher ($3-8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). Two parallel trend lines can be drawn for the two wind regimes. Below $-14 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, there is a cluster of points that are clearly outliers compared to the two trend lines. The density is much higher then expected for these temperatures. The relatively high densities for these points could be caused by high windspeeds but this is not the case, the windspeed is around 5 m s^{-1} which is not extremely high. The relative humidity is around 90 %, this is approximately the same as the other measurements which have a much lower density.

It is interesting to know if the cluster of points with this relatively high density are just random error in the measurements or if this has a physical reason. Figure 5.3(f) shows that the measurements of this cluster are from three different dates, it is thus not very likely that an instrumental error occurred during these three different measurement periods. A reversal to higher densities at temperatures colder than $-15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was already suggested by Grant and Rhea (1974) and a similar weak effect was seen by Judson and Doesken (2000). The snow morphology diagram, (Figure 5.1), shows that there are no dendrites for colder temperatures and sector plates maybe smaller crystals. Since the shape of the plates leads to a higher compaction in comparison to the dendrites, it is likely that the density increases with an increasing amount of plates.

To investigate the effect of different crystal shapes on the density of new snow, it is desirable to have measurements for low temperatures in combination with low windspeeds. It is then possible to make a comparison of the microstructure of the crystals for different temperatures, without wind influence. In the dataset of season 05/06, the measurements below $-15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ where the density is high are always in combination with moderate windspeeds. It is therefore difficult to compare the crystals and distinguish the influence of wind and temperature. In the data set of Hendriks (2002) we found density measurements in the required temperature regime. This data set is shown in Figure 5.10(a). There are two points with an air temperature of approximately $-15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at low windspeeds with densities around 80 kg m^{-3} . Assuming a linear decrease of density with decreasing air temperature, a much lower density as 80 kg m^{-3} is expected. The influence of windspeed is negligible for these measurements so the growth mechanism should be the dominant factor in this density increase.

The crystals found in the lower temperature regime ($T_a \leq -14 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, no wind) for the dataset of season 01/02 were plates and columns. For higher temperatures ($13 < T_a < -12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, no wind) in the dataset of season 05/06 dendritic crystals were found.

Hence it is plausible that the density increases for temperatures below $-14 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, due to the different crystal shapes and sizes. The dependence of density on air temperature would then be parabolic, with a minimum around $-14 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Two parallel modes are possible as determined by the windspeed. This is a very qualitative conclusion. It would be interesting though to have more measurements with low temperatures to examine if the density reversal always takes place.

It is clear that the current discontinuity in the density prediction is not realistic. However, due to a lack of data in this range, no further effort was made to find a possible plausible fit.

5.2 Older data sets

The dataset on which the current density parametrization in SNOWPACK is based was assembled in the winter season of 97/98. At the time of writing, the only data available was the measured density and the meteorological parameters measured. Details about the shape and size of the crystals were not known. Furthermore, no video camera was used and information about surface processes was not available. It was therefore not possible to examine the dataset as thoroughly as the current dataset (season 05/06). The original dataset contained 104 measurements, and the final statistical model was based on 70 degrees of freedom. This means that 32 outliers were removed. It is unclear if this was done for statistical reasons, and therefore if the statistical analyses of season 97/98 and season 05/06 are comparable. In consequence,

Figure 5.10: Measured density for season 01/02 and 97/98 plotted against air temperature (squares), colours indicate windspeed, the black circles represent the data of season 05/06 .

Parameter	Value	Variable	Unit	Season 97/98	Season 05/06
α	70				
β	6.5				
γ	7.5	Density	kg m^{-3}	32 to 125	26 to 174
δ	0.26	Air temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	-9.9 to 6.6	-20 to -3.8
η	13	Snow surface temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	-11.9 to -0.5	-20 to -2.9
ϕ	-4.5	Relative humidity	%	46 to 99	71 to 100
μ	-0.65	Windspeed	m s^{-1}	0 to 6	0 to 8
ν	-0.17				
o	0.06				

Table 5.5: Parameters for density parametrization 97/98 (left), and ranges of measured variables (right)

the outliers discussed above will be removed in this analysis.

An additional dataset (Hendriks, 2002) which is an addition to the dataset of Perret (2000) was examined. These two sets were treated as one dataset. The combined dataset was not used for current density prediction in SNOWPACK since it was considered not to be consistent enough.

In this section, a comparison is made between the measured densities in seasons 97/98, 01/02 and 05/06, and the predicted densities of the old and new statistical models.

5.2.1 Comparison of the old and new density models

The current parametrization for the new snow density used in SNOWPACK is:

$$\rho = \alpha + \beta T_a + \gamma T_{ss} + \delta RH + \eta VW + \phi T_a T_{ss} + \mu T_a VW + \nu RH VW + o T_a T_{ss} RH, \quad (5.1)$$

the values for the different coefficients are listed in table 5.5. To compare the two statistical models, density predictions for the different seasons 97/98, 01/02 and 05/06 were examined. The measured densities were compared with the predicted densities for the three seasons. The results are shown in Figure 5.13. The correlation coefficients between the predictions and measured densities are listed in table 5.6.

The values in table 5.6 indicate that the predictions of the old model are very poor, with correlation coefficients of 0.18 and -0.15 for seasons 01/02 and 05/06 respectively. The new model predictions had a correlation coefficient of 0.47 and 0.52 for seasons 97/98 and 01/02 which is already quite an improvement. A reason for the poor correlations between the measurements and model values could be (i) the high level of collinearity in the model terms of 97/98 and (ii) the differing ranges of data.

(i) A regression analysis was performed on the old dataset in order to test if the same coefficients could be derived. The regression analysis in 97/98 was conducted slightly differently. The mean of all the density measurements was found, and before performing the regression analysis, the mean density was subtracted from the different density measurements. The regression was then performed without an intercept term. This analysis has been repeated and the numerical results are shown in table 5.7, the residual plots are shown in Figure 5.2.1 and 5.2.1. Although the values for the coefficients differ from those in table 5.5, the signs are the same. The different values for the coefficients might have originated from an unknown method of analysis. What the parameters in table 5.7 show, is that some terms may seem significant. However, they are highly collinear (values up to 0.975). It is not known if the collinearity was analysed in 97/98. High collinearity results in poorly determined coefficients, slight changes in input data has then a major influence on the weight of the different terms. This may lead to very unstable predictions. Furthermore, the residual plots (Figures 5.2.1 and 5.2.1) show very "extreme" curves, therefore there are some significant errors in the model.

(ii) In this analysis, the density measured in 97/98 was plotted against the different meteo variables in Figure 5.14. The ranges of the measured variables are listed in table 5.5. The dataset 05/06 covers a wider range than the 97/98 dataset, except for the relative humidity. However the measurements in the 05/06 dataset with relative humidity lower than 70 % were considered outliers and therefore left out of the analysis. Because of the lack of control data (video), this could not be done for the 97/98 dataset.

The two datasets do not only differ in range of the measured variables but also in the distribution of the measurements over the ranges. The temperature plot for example (Figure 5.14(a)), shows that most measurements in 97/98 were done when air temperature was between approximately -4 and 0 °C. Whereas in season 05/06 almost no measurements were taken in this temperature range. A similar feature is seen in the humidity plot (Figure 5.14(c)). Most of the measurements were done when relative humidity was between 90 and 100 %, in the season 05/06 most measurements were made between 70 and 95 %. In Figure 5.15, an overview is shown of the distributions of the different variables over the measured ranges. The distributions show that the two different datasets are assembled in different conditions and it is therefore difficult to make a good comparison.

In addition, most measurements in 97/98 were conducted in Davos with an altitude of 1560m above sea level, whereas the measurements in 05/06 were all made in the Versuchsfeld at 2540m above sea level. By comparing the different data sets, we are not only comparing different sensors but also different locations. This makes it very difficult to compare the two data sets. By measuring in Davos, the measurements are automatically restricted to a higher temperature range. In a way, this is good because density predictions are also needed for lower stations. However, it is questionable if the density measured in Davos at a certain temperature is the same as that measured in the Versuchsfeld at that certain temperature.

A poor model was obtained by performing a regression analysis with both the data of 97/98 and 05/06

Predicted density	Measured density		
	97/98	01/02	05/06
Modelled old	0.9090911	0.1854789	-0.1036429
Modelled new	0.4097278	0.5643261	0.81880236

Table 5.6: Correlation coefficients of measured and predicted densities for the three seasons

Figure 5.11: Residual plots 97/98. Residuals against fitted values (upper left), absolute standardized residuals against fitted values (upper right), QQ plot(lower left), Leverage plot(lower right).

Figure 5.12: Residual plots 97/98. Residuals against temperature (upper left), residuals against snow surface temperature (upper right), residuals against relative humidity (lower left), residuals against windspeed (lower right).

	coef	stcoef	signif	R2.x	p.value
β	6.54777821	0.91424222	2.6244935	0.7440436	0.0000
γ	7.24136676	0.96430989	3.3448156	0.7749231	0.0000
δ	0.26548459	0.14575312	3.8102742	0.6684795	0.0000
η	10.36762796	0.57096956	1.0535692	0.8965381	0.0393
ϕ	-4.89545986	-6.04757119	-1.6049180	0.9755068	0.0021
μ	-0.27427381	-0.08653687	-0.2914632	0.6951562	0.5623
ν	-0.13185015	-0.60402769	-1.0684154	0.9043480	0.0367
o	0.06387783	7.14174713	1.9429044	0.9749705	0.0003
St.dev.error: 8.682 on 62 degrees of freedom					
Multiple R ² : 0.8388 Adjusted R-squared: 0.8206					
F-statistic: 40.32 on 8 and 62 d.f., p.value: 0					

Table 5.7: Regression with terms of 97/98, the intercept α (mean density) is 70

combined. This is mainly due to the low densities measured in the temperature regime close to 0 °C in the dataset of 97/98. There were two clusters, one cluster has a mean density that is far too low according to the trend in the dataset of 05/06, the upper cluster comes close to this trend. The lower cluster represents one day of measurements. This could be due to special prevailing meteorological conditions. It is not clear what causes relatively high densities in this temperature regime.

The data set of 01/02 is reasonably well predicted by the new model. Especially if the relative humidity is removed as a predictor. In the data set of 01/02, the correlation between density and relative humidity is 0. If we ignore the relative humidity in the new model, the overall performance of the model decreases slightly for season 05/06 (the adjusted R² value decreases from 0.73 to 0.57). However, the prediction for season 01/02 improves with a correlation coefficient of 0.7894190 between measured and predicted density.

Overall, it can be concluded that the new model performed better for both seasons 01/02 and 05/06. The measured densities of Hendrikx (2002) were fairly well predicted. A larger range in meteorological parameters is covered. The only remaining problem is predicting densities at temperatures close to 0 °C. In this temperature range, large differences exist between the data set assembled in 97/98 and the densities that are expected based on the two data sets assembled in 01/02 and 05/06.

Figure 5.13: Measured against predicted density.

Figure 5.14: Measured density plotted against meteo variables, season 97/98.

Figure 5.15: Distribution of measurements over different ranges for the two datasets of 97/98 and 05/06.

5.3 Density and SMP measurements

In the new snow profiles (Chapter 3) SMP measurements were conducted and density profiles were made. Differences in hardness of certain layers are important in the process of avalanche formation. Although density is not always a direct measure for mechanical properties of snow, knowledge about the density profile in the snowpack gives avalanche forecasters additional information about the stability of the snowpack. A sudden decrease in density above a hard layer could be potential weak layer for example. Digging snow pits and making density profiles is time consuming, therefore, tried was to find a relation between high resolution resistance measurements of the SMP and the density profiles. In practice this could for example mean that once the first density and SMP profiles are known, only SMP measurements would be necessary in the days after to obtain information about the development of the snowpack.

The profiles were made on a relatively high interval (in the order of days). In total, 5 SMP measurements were conducted in front of each profile with a horizontal distance of 50 cm in between. Found was that in spite of some spatial variability, the main features in the SMP signals were the same.

Figure 5.3 shows an typical example SMP measurements. The change in signal was purely due to settling of the new snow itself. In between the profiles, no extra snow was added to the snowpack. The red line shows the resistance on the 19th of January 14:00. The point $z=0$ is the snow surface. Despite the very small forces (not higher than 0.45 N), different layers were detected by the SMP. The most clear layers were the relatively low dense layer at ± 23 cm and the old snow layer at ± 42 cm depth. Interesting is the SMP signal on 20 January 09:30. The old snowlayer was used as a reference, assumed is that the settling of the old snow layers is negligible in comparison with the settling of the new snow layer. The snowpack settles ± 5 cm according to the SMP measurements. This is confirmed by the snowdepth measurements over the snowboards. All the peaks and troughs were shifted slightly downward and the resistance increased. By the settling of the new snow, especially the low density layers were compressed. The trough caused by the layer at ± 23 cm on the 19th is compacted to almost half the width on the 20th of January as an example. In order to test if there was a relationship between the SMP signal and the measured densities, the SMP signal was averaged over the vertical resolution of the measured density (3 cm). The results are shown in Figures 5.17(a) and 5.17(b) for profiles in March and April respectively. The different colours correspond to the different profile dates. Figure 5.17(a) shows profiles in April. The blue triangles that correspond to the first profile clearly show a relationship between the resistance and the density. The relationship is surprisingly linear. The second profile (green squares) shows similar features. Except for one outlier, all the data points are slightly shifted to higher resistance values and higher densities. The two sets of data points show clearly that densification occurred. In this process, the resistance is increasing slightly. The profile in the 17th of April (red dots) shows a linear increase of density with increasing resistance as well. However, the increase in density with increasing resistance is much smaller. The three profiles revealed two stages in the settling process.

The first two days are characterised by the so called 'abbauende metamorfose', also called grain boundary diffusion sintering. In this stage, the crystals loose their dendricity and become smaller due to local vapour diffusion. The mechanical properties of the snow do not change strongly in this stage, densification takes place in absence of a large increase in resistance.

The second stage shown in Figure 5.17(a) is characterised by a relatively large increase in resistance and a relatively small increase in density. The mechanical properties are changing in this stage due to larger temperature gradients. The larger temperature gradients are the motor for intergranular vapour diffusion transport or 'evaporation condensation sintering'. Vapour transports occurs not only locally but over larger distances between the grains. In this stage, the grains and bonds start to grow, resulting in a higher resistance for similar densities.

Figure 5.17(b) shows the profiles that were made in March. Although the plot show more outliers, the dominant trends are similar to the ones in April. Again a strong increase in density with slight increase in resistance for the first two profiles. The last profile shows a stronger increase in resistance in lower increase in density. The second set of datapoints (green squares) shows more outliers and is not as smooth and linear as the one in April. This may be due to the different time difference between the two profiles. In April, the difference was one day between the first two profiles, in March the difference is 3 days. It may be that the profile on 13.03 is more a crossover between the two processes described above whereas these processes were more distinguished in April.

Figure 5.16: SMP output for profiles on 19.01 and 20.01, $z=0$ is the snow surface.

Figures 5.17(c) and 5.17(d) show the density plotted against resistance and relative height (colours). The relative depth is introduced to allow comparison of the position of the different datapoints in the snowpack. For both snowfalls in March and April, extra snowfall occurred after the first profile. Datapoints with values that vary between 0 and 1 belong to the snowfall prior to the first snowfall. Datapoints with relative height values above one correspond to snow that came after the first profile.

Figure 5.17(c) shows that for most datapoints, the increase in density and resistance is accompanied by a gradual decrease in relative depth (relative depth). Some outliers appear, this may be due to for example surface processes (wind, sun crust) and are not representative for the settling process.

Interesting is if the figures above have a potential to be used as a verification of SNOWPACK. In Figure 5.18 the different grain types throughout the profiles are shown. The grain types for the different profiles clearly show a development, from dendritic new snow crystals to rounded or faceted crystals. It is difficult at this stage to make a qualitative analysis and to link the shape of the curves in 5.17 to the grain types modelled with SNOWPACK. For a quantitative analysis, the iso-octane samples obtained from the profiles should be analysed. Another idea for future use would be incorporating the temperature gradients in SNOWPACK in the settling description. Once the temperature gradients are larger, the rate of densification decreases and mechanical changes take place in the snow microstructure. The SMP measurements show clearly a potential in this direction, but it is not totally clear yet in which direction to head.

Figure 5.17: Density against resistance for three different profiles in April (a) and March (b). Density against resistance and relative depth for three profiles in April (c) and March (d).

Figure 5.18: Different grain types modelled by SNOWPACK, 10.03 (a), 13.03 (b) and 20.03 (c).

Chapter 6

SNOWPACK simulations

6.1 Implementation of the new density model in SNOWPACK

To test the effect of the new density model in SNOWPACK, the season 2005/2006 was simulated with both old and new density models. The results were compared with regular monthly profiles and with three specific snowfall events. Three different snowfalls in high-, -mid and late winter were analysed. The total mass of the regular profiles was measured from the surface to the bottom of the snowpack, the mass of the specific snowfalls were measured over the snowboards which were placed on the surface before the snowfall started (see Chapter 3). The model was run with prescribed snowdepth and no corrections were made. In addition, certain layers were marked and followed throughout the model runs in order to compare the modelled settling curves with the settling curves of the snow harps. To perform an independent test of the new density model, a model run for season 1995/1996 was also made.

6.1.1 Comparison with profiles 2005/2006

Total mass and density profiles

The total mass of the snowpack measured in the regular profiles was compared with the modelled mass of the two model versions, being the new and old density model. The measured and modelled masses for the profiles are shown in Figure 6.1(a). The modelled masses are interpolated to the measured snowdepths of the profiles according to

$$\text{Mass} = \frac{\text{Mass}_{mod}}{\text{HS}_{mod}} \text{HS}, \quad (6.1)$$

where HS is the snowdepth, Mass the measured mass in the regular profiles and Mass_{mod} the modelled mass. At the start of the season, both density models predict a mass that is approximately 30 kg m^{-2} too low. The mass predictions for January and February are reasonably correct. In March, the error increases slightly, where the new model predictions are closer to the measured mass than the old model predictions. Whereas the modelled masses were too low for most profiles, the modelled mass for the final profile in June is too high for both models. The old density model is closer to the measured mass in June than the new model. The mean error in mass prediction for all the profiles is $\pm 30.3 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$ for the old model and $\pm 27 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$ for the new model.

It is surprising that in spite of the consequent underestimation of new snow density in the old model (section 5.2.1), the errors in predicted masses are small and do not differ substantially from the masses predicted with the use of the new density model. An explanation might be the way in which new snow is treated in SNOWPACK. The current settling is related to the old density model, with low densities. This implies higher settling rates (2.1.1). The snowdepth is prescribed, thus more snow is added to the snowpack, that is: the intensity of the snowfall virtually increases. In this way, more snow is added and despite the low initial densities a higher correct total mass is obtained in the end. Figure 6.1(b) illustrates the effect described

Figure 6.1: Comparison of measured and modelled total mass of the snowpack (a) and modelled and measured settling curves in January 2006 (b).

above. The settling curves of the old model are steeper in the first few hours after snowfall than the settling curves of the new model. The underestimation of the initial new snow density causes a high settling rate. The total measured and modelled mass of the different snowfalls are shown in table 6.1. The modelled masses of the first two snowfalls (January and March) are too high in comparison with the measured mass. Both modelled masses are too high, the new density model gives a larger error than the old density model. The errors of the old and new density models are +4 kg m⁻² and +9 kg m⁻² respectively for the first snowfall and +12 kg m⁻² and +17 kg m⁻² for the second snowfall respectively. The modelled mass of the third snowfall is too low for the old model with an error of -9 kg m⁻², the new model gives approximately the correct mass.

It is difficult to conduct a proper analysis of the mass balance with the new density model since SNOWPACK is tuned to the old density model. The settling routines are tuned to densities that are too low in most cases. As discussed above, drawing conclusions from table 6.1 is difficult. More insight into the

	Measured (kg m ⁻²)	Old density model (kg m ⁻²)	New density model (kg m ⁻²)
18-19 January	47.5	51.6	56.4
03-13 March	97	108.7	113.7
10-14 April	50	41.1	49.7

Table 6.1: Measured and modelled new snowfall masses

performance of the density models is given in figure 6.2, which shows the measured and modelled density profiles of the three snowfalls. The modelled densities are averaged over vertical resolution depth of the measured density (3 cm).

The modelled values for the density of the different layers are approximately in the correct range. However, the new model shows more structure, partly quite similar to the measured profiles.

In the first period (December) there is densification at 105 cm in the measured profile, in the old density profile, this densification is not seen while in the new density model, a denser layer is located at 105 cm. The decrease in density from 125-110 cm is not seen in the old density profile while the new density model shows this decrease. The relatively strong changes in density throughout the profile are not seen in the old density profile, however the profile of the new model shows the same structure, the changes are not as strong as in the measured profile.

The second period (March) shows the same features as described above. Again the old model does not show the structure that is seen in the actual measurements. The density is gradually increasing with depth. In both the new model profile and measured profile, a more dense layer is present close to the surface, underneath this layer density is decreasing. Both measured and new modelled profiles show similar features. The measured profile of the third period (April) does not show a strong changes densities. The top layer has a relatively low density, this is barely seen in the old model profile. The middle part of the measured profile does not show large density changes while this is seen in the new modelled profile. The decrease in density in the old density profile at 190 cm is not seen in the measurements, there is even a very small densification in the measurements in this layer. The decrease in density at the lower most layer that the two models show is not seen in the measured profile.

Although it is difficult to make a quantitative analysis at this stage about the performance of the two density models, it is clear that the new model is able to reproduce features that are seen in the measurements, on the contrary the old model is not able to reproduce these features.

Predicted mass for season 95/96

As the new snow density model was calibrated for season 05/06, a test on another winter season could reveal whether the new model resolves the problems encountered thus far. This season 1995/1996 was chosen since measurements with snowharps were also made in this season which may be helpful in further analysis. The predicted mass of the two models were again compared with the measured mass in the profiles. The predicted and measured masses are shown in Figure 6.3(a). For most profiles, the old and new model give approximately the same mass. In six out of eight cases, the two models give the same mass. The new model performs slightly better in two profiles. In general, the predicted masses are too low with errors up to $\pm 15\%$.

Modelled settling curves of the harps used in season 95/96 are shown in Figure 6.3(b). The plot shows that the settling curves of both models are close to each other. This is not surprising since the mass predictions do not differ substantially. For harp number two, the curves are different in such a way that the old model settles faster in the first few hours after placement. In general the results are the same as seen for season 05/06: Underestimation of the mass and settling rates that are too low.

Figure 6.2: Measured and modelled density profiles for three different snowfall periods in January (a), March (b) and April 2006 (c).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.3: Comparison of measured and modelled total mass of the snowpack (a) and modelled and measured settling curves in 1996 (b).

6.2 Settling

With the correct initial mass as described above, the settling description in SNOWPACK was examined by comparing the measured settling curves of the harps with the predicted settling curves of SNOWPACK. In total, 11 harps were placed. All the harps were functioning well, harp height and snow temperature were measured without major problems for every harp. The western and eastern sides of the harps were measured separately. A slight difference in height of the two sides occurs sometimes when the snow surface is angulated. In this case, the difference between the harp sides remains constant over time. Therefore the mean height of the two sides was taken. Except for harp number 10 where only the west side was taken since the east side was not reliable. In Figure 6.4(a), the mean heights of the harps are shown. Figure

Figure 6.4: Measured height (a) and temperature (b) respectively of the different harps.

6.4(a) shows that there was strong settling of the snowpack after relatively big snowfalls. The snowfall events in December and March which are indicated with an arrow in Figure 6.4(a) are an example. The first few days after the snowfall, strong settling took place. After this, settling became weaker. Especially the first 4 lower harps settled very slowly throughout the season. In this part of the snowpack, almost nothing occurred regarding settling. Remarkable is the 'kink' around the third of May, where the settling was suddenly stronger. This occurred firstly to the upper harps and a few days later to the harps deeper in the snowpack. In Figure 6.4(b) the temperatures of the harps are plotted. An increase in temperature occurs in this same period. This increase is the result of infiltrating meltwater. Due to this, grains transform to wet grains and this causes stronger settling. Furthermore, the temperature plot shows that the snowpack became isothermal from the twenty fourth of March. The temperatures of the harps came closer to each other from this date and the overall temperature in the snowpack drops closer to the bottom temperature. In case of snowcover, the bottom temperature is always 0 °C. The daily variation is clearly visible at the beginning of all temperature curves, the harps were near the surface in the first few days of placement and the harp temperature was strongly influenced by the penetrating short wave radiation.

In SNOWPACK, the specific layers at the surface which correspond to the time of harp placement were tagged. In this way, a comparison of measured and modelled settling curves was made possible. In Figure 6.5(a) the measured and predicted settling curves of the new model version are shown. It is difficult to draw conclusions from Figure 6.5(a) because errors made in the lower part of the snowpack accumulate and cause larger errors in the upper part of the snowpack. Different errors compensate, which results in settling curves that look reasonably well modelled. However, they can be inaccurate. The initial settling of the first harp seems to be reasonably well modelled. After the first stage, the distance between the modelled curves and the measured curve becomes larger. The mass prediction of SNOWACK on the 15th of December was too

small by a factor 1.5. In fact, the first modelled settling curve was based on a snowpack in which there was a large shortage off mass and was therefore not realistic.

In order to examine the settling process more thoroughly, a correction was carried out. The measured density profile of the snowpit that was made on 15.12.2005 was prescribed and model runs were made for season 05/06. The correction was made to isolate problems that occurred during the beginning of the season and to focus on the specific settling processes. Settling curves for the model runs that were made after the density correction are shown in figure 6.6(a) After the correction, the density in the lower part of

Figure 6.5: Measured and modelled settling curves. The solid red line is the modelled snowdepth, the dotted blue line the measured snowdepth, the solid blue line is the measured height of the different harps, the dotted black line is the modelled height of the different harps. Uncorrected (a) and density corrected on 15.12.2005 (b).

the snowpack was assumed to be approximately correct. The measured and modelled curves of the lowest four harps are quite close together after the 23rd of January. However, in the initial phase of the settling process, directly after the snowfall the predicted curves were incorrect. The model settles too slow. Since the problem was not the initial new snow density, the settling routines in SNOWPACK. were examined more closely. As described in section 2.1.1 the settling rate in SNOWPACK is dependent on the viscosity. It is assumed that the ice behaves as a viscoelastic material. The description of the strain rate differs slightly from equation 2.10, an extra term σ_0 was added. This term was introduced to account for settling that is not only due to the weight of the elements in the snowpack but also for settling due to metamorphism. Snow in the upper part of the snowpack (at the surface for example), also settles. However, this is not due to applied stress. With the term σ_0 , virtual weight is added to account for this process:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_v = \frac{\sigma_s + \sigma_0}{\eta_s}, \quad (6.2)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_v$ is the viscous strain rate, σ_s the mean stress, σ_0 the extra virtual stress and η_s the snow viscosity. The mean stress is simply determined by integrating weights of all the elements over the vertical. Changing the settling process would mean changing σ_0 or η_s . The term σ_0 is described as:

$$\sigma_0 = S \frac{\sigma_t}{r_g}, \quad (6.3)$$

where $\sigma_t = 0.11 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ the ice surface tension, r_g the grain diameter and S the shape factor defined as

$$S = 1.5 + 2\sqrt{dd}, \quad (6.4)$$

with dd the dendricity. Since the dendricity plays a role in the determination of σ_0 , the stronger settling rates caused by σ_0 are gradually decreasing as the dendricity decreases when the snow ages.

The viscosity is described as

$$\eta_s = \frac{N_3 \theta_i}{4} \left(\frac{r_b}{r_g} \right)^2 \left(\frac{l_n + 2r_g}{l_n} \right) \eta_0, \quad (6.5)$$

where N the coordination number which gives the amount of bond per grain and determines the inter-connectivity of the ice matrix, θ_i the volumetric ice content, r_b the bond size, l_n the neck length and η_0 is

$$\eta_0 = \frac{\sigma_1^3}{\epsilon_1 (T_R, \sigma_1) F_\eta^3 \sigma_{ncrit}^2} e^{-\frac{Q}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_R} - \frac{1}{T} \right]}. \quad (6.6)$$

where $\sigma_1 = 0.5 \times 10^6$ Pa a reference stress value, $\epsilon_1 = 1.76 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$ a reference strain rate value, $\sigma_{ncrit} = 0.4 \times 10^6$ Pa the critical neck stress, $Q = 67000 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$ an empirical constant for activation energy, $R = 8.31 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ the universal gas constant, T the temperature (K) and $T_R = 263 \text{ K}$ a reference temperature. The term F_η is an empirical parameter and is written as:

$$F_\eta = F_{time} * FT + \frac{F_{ice}}{\theta_i} + F_{water} \frac{\theta_w}{\theta_i}, \quad (6.7)$$

where F_{ice} and F_{water} are constants. $F_{time} * FT$ takes in account the 'age' and shape of the grains. It is defined as

$$F_{time} = 2.1\sqrt{dd} + 0.7sp, \quad (6.8)$$

and

$$FT = 1 - \frac{Julian_p - Julian_c}{90}, \quad (6.9)$$

where $Julian_p$ is the present time and $Julian_c$ is the time of creation of the element. If the difference between present time and time of creation is 90 days, the snow is regarded to be old and the time factor is negligible. As the snow ages, the dendricity decreases and thus F_η decreases. This results in a higher viscosity and therefore lower settling rates.

It is difficult to develop a description of the viscosity of new snow on a solid physical basis since little is known on this subject. Therefore attempts to improve the settling routines in SNOWPACK were very qualitative. In order to generate a better understanding of the settling process in SNOWPACK, several sensitivity test were conducted with the fudge term F_η . The other terms in equation 6.6 were kept constant.

A case study was performed on the snowfall event in March. A measured profile was taken again to initialize runs over this snowfall event. The profile from 27th of February was used. The reason is that density measurements were not yet conducted for the snowfall in December. For the period in December it was therefore difficult to test if the new snow densities were correct. The measured and modelled settling curves of the snowfalls in December and March are shown in Figures 6.6(a) and 6.6(b). The density profiles were prescribed in SNOWPACK before the snowfalls started. This case study focussed on the first few days after the snowfall.

For both the snowfall periods, the curves show similar features. The first (lowest) modelled curves settle too slow. The second (upper) modelled curve matches quite well with the measured curve for approximately the first two days after placement. The consequent underestimation of settling by SNOWPACK could be due to viscosities which were too high for new snow. To examine the influence of the different factors that play a role in the viscosity description, the snowfall period in March was investigated, since this snowfall was completely monitored. The snowfall in March can be divided into three subsnowfalls with the first snowfall starting around the 6th of March. To these subsnowfalls will be referred as snowfall I, II and III, as indicated in Figure 6.6(c).

Figure 6.6: Measured and modelled settling curves in December (a) and March (b). Solid red line is modelled HS, dotted blue line is measured HS, solid blue lines are measured harp heights, dashed black lines are modelled harp heights. Increased dd in fudge (c), varied dd in fudge (d).

For new snow, the dendricity parameter is set to one in SNOWPACK. During the metamorphism of the crystals, dendricity gradually decreases towards zero. The time stage on which the focus is on is exactly the time stage where dendricity is present. This is clearly shown in Figure 6.7(a) which shows the modelled dendricity. Increasing the weight of the dendricity in expression 6.8 by a factor 4 led to the settling curves shown in Figure 6.6(c). The upper modelled curve matches the measured curve better than in Figure 6.6(b). Both the first and second modelled curves are closer to the measured curve. Although the measured and modelled curves are closer to each other, the lower model curve still does not show the trend that the harp shows. In the first stage, the model almost does not settle while the harp clearly settles quickly.

After the initial stage, the dendricity of grains is negligible and this parameter does not play a role in settling. So during the initial phase the effect of dendricity should be enhanced.

In order to test the influence of the dendricity on the modelled settling, the factor $2.1 * dd$ in expression 6.8 was varied between 0.5 and 6 times the original value. The result is plotted in Figure 6.6(d). The initial phase of settling is more realistically modelled for the larger factors. However, the first tag still does not settle enough. Increasing the weight of the dendricity in the F_{time} term has a larger effect on the upper modelled curve despite the fact that the time period in which dendricity is present (red colour in Figure 6.7(a)) is approximately the same for both tags. Therefore it may be possible that dendricity is not the most dominant factor in the initial stage. Figure 6.7(b) shows the modelled density. At the time that the tagging started there is a slight difference in density. The new snow density at time of placement of the first harp is around 125 kg m^{-3} and the new snow density at time of placement of the second harp is around 75 kg m^{-3} . While the initial development of dendricity was the same for both subsnowfalls I and II, the difference in density may be more dominant in the settling process.

The new snow measurements during the snowfall also show lower densities for the second part of the snowfall. While the difference in density is observed, the first harp shows strong settling in comparison with SNOWPACK. It may be that SNOWPACK gives too much weight to the density in the description for the fudge (equation 6.7). To test the influence of this term, F_{ice} in equation 6.7 was varied from a factor 0.5-3.0. The result is shown in Figure 6.6(e). The influence of F_{ice} is clearly larger than the influence of the dendricity in F_{time} . The settling is very strong for the larger factors 2 and 3. By reducing the original value by half, the settling clearly weakens.

The lower tag shows that changing F_{ice} can contribute to an improved modelling of the settling in the first stage. However, F_{ice} influences the settling but does not differentiate enough between the initial phase where the settling is strong and the period after which settling weakens. Figure 6.6(f) shows the settling curves where the term F_{ice} was multiplied by a factor $(1 + dd)$. There was a slight improvement in the matching of the curves, however the modelled curves in the lower part still do not distinguish enough between the two different settling stages.

The parameters that were varied above influence the rate of settling, however the shape of the settling curves changed only slightly. The measured curves clearly show a distinction between the first stage of settling where the settling is strong and the final stage at which the settling levels. In order to provide more insight into the way the two different stages of settling are treated in SNOWPACK, a comparison was made with the settling description that was used in the SN THERM model.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.7: (a) Modelled dendricity in the snowpack. (b) Modelled density in the snowpack.

In SNTHERM, the approach of Anderson (1976, p. 36-39, 82-83), is followed. The settling process is considered to be in two stages. The initial settling is due to metamorphism and further settling occurs due to overburden. The rate for compaction during the settling due to metamorphism is described by:

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Delta z} \frac{\partial \Delta z}{\partial t} \right]_{\text{metamorphism}} = -2.778 \times 10^{-6} \times c3 \times c4 \times e^{-0.04(273.15-T)}, \quad (6.10)$$

where

$$c3 = c4 = 1 \quad \text{if } \gamma_i = 0 \text{ and } \gamma_i \leq 150 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \quad (6.11)$$

$$c3 = e^{[-0.046(\gamma_i - 150)]} \quad \text{if } \gamma_i > 150 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \quad (6.12)$$

$$c4 = 2 \quad \text{if } \gamma_l > 0, \quad (6.13)$$

where $\gamma_I = \theta_i$ gives the density and γ_l the liquid water content. The equation above predicts a deformation rate of 1 % per hour for snow densities less than 150 kg m⁻³. The settling due to overburden reads

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Delta z} \frac{\partial \Delta z}{\partial t} \right]_{\text{overburden}} = -\frac{P_s}{\eta_0} e^{-c5(273.15-T)} e^{-c6\rho_s}, \quad (6.14)$$

where $\eta_0 = 3.6 \times 10^6 \text{ N s m}^{-2}$, $c5 = 0.08 \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $c6 = 0.021 \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$.

The settling by metamorphism and overburden in SNOWPACK was represented by (6.2)

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Delta z} \frac{\partial \Delta z}{\partial t} \right]_{\text{metamorphismSP}} = \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta},$$

and

$$\left[\frac{1}{\Delta z} \frac{\partial \Delta z}{\partial t} \right]_{\text{overburdenSP}} = \frac{\sigma}{\eta},$$

respectively. Equations 6.10 and 6.14 are implemented in SNOWPACK in order to compare the magnitude of settling rates according to the different descriptions. The compaction rates (% h⁻¹) due to metamorphism are shown in Figures 6.8(a) and 6.8(b). For display purposes the colour range in Figure 6.8 is limited to -1.5-0 % h⁻¹. The maximum compaction rate due to metamorphism in SNOWPACK is approximately 15 % h⁻¹. This is large compared to the maximum values of approximately 1 % h⁻¹ compaction rates expected by the description in SNTHERM. However, in reality compaction rates can increase by at least an order of magnitude for intense snowfalls of soft snow (Gray et al. 1979 (1979)) or when there are strong winds. So the relatively high compaction rates of SNOWPACK are not very unrealistic.

The settling rates due to metamorphism for both models SNOWPACK and SNTHERM are shown in Figure 6.8. The colours represent compaction rates on a scale from -1.5 % (blue) to 0 % (red). Red is the dominant colour in Figure 6.8(a) which represents metamorphism settling rates for SNOWPACK being around 0 % h⁻¹. On the contrary, green/yellow is more dominant in Figure 6.8(b), which represents settling rates around -0.7 and -1 % h⁻¹ for SNTHERM. High settling rates (blue) seen in SNOWPACK are not present in SNTHERM.

So in general, for SNOWPACK, the settling due to metamorphism is more or less separated into two regimes, mainly red (settling rates around zero) and some parts blue/green (settling rates of -0.7 % h⁻¹ and higher). In contrast the settling rates for SNTHERM are more evenly distributed, a large green section near the surface and a deeper red section in the snowpack. This is indicated by the arrows in Figures 6.8(a) and 6.8(b).

In the lower part of the snowpack (140-155 cm), SNOWPACK does not show any settling due to metamorphism. On the contrary, SNTHERM in Figure 6.8(b) shows settling rates between -0.7 and -1 % h⁻¹. In the lower section of the snowpack the error with the harps develops, the harps settles to slow. SNOWPACK shows very low settling rates compared to SNTHERM in this region.

The settling rates due to overburden in SNOWPACK are shown in Figure 6.9. In the snowfall period, the values for the overburden settling rate are very small with values between 0 and 0.2 % h⁻¹. Settling due

to overburden remains zero during subsnowfall I. In this case, both the settling due to metamorphism and overburden are zero. It is remarkable that the snow in the lower section (indicated with the blue arrow in Figure 6.9 of the snowpack is almost not reacting to the mass added during subsnowfall I. After a large increase in snowdepth during sub snowfall II settling due to overburden takes place in the lower snowpack (indicated by pink arrow).

The overload was simply determined by the integral over the vertical of the weights of the elements. Equation 6.2 leads to the conclusion that in the case of only very small settling, the viscosity must be too high. Figure 6.9(b) shows the modelled viscosity. At the point indicated with an arrow, the viscosity increased shortly up to 10 GPa s, at the beginning of subsnowfall I the viscosity has values around 5 GPa s. The fact that the viscosity increases in the old snow layer so quickly might prevent this layer from settling when it is snowed in during subsnowfall I. So, the problems encountered with the settling descriptions are probably not errors of the description of the snow during snowfall but more the description of the snow in the old snowcover.

Viscosity is also a function of temperature. A decrease in temperature results in an increase in viscosity according to equation 6.6. Figure 6.10 shows a drop (values down to -20°) in modelled temperature before subsnowfall I and relatively high (-5 to 0°C) temperature during sub snowfall II. The region with low temperatures during sub snowfall I is exactly the region in which the problems with the settling occurred. The region in which the predictions were approximately correct correspond to the warmer regions in the snowpack. The influence of the temperature term on the settling should therefore be more intensively tested.

In general, more systematic sensitivity tests are needed to isolate the influence of the different terms which play a role in the settling process. Microstructure parameters such as bond and grain size were not taken into account in this quick analysis and may play an important role as well. Test runs should be set up to isolate specific problems and provide an improved detailed error analysis.

Figure 6.8: (a) Sig0/eta SNOWPACK. (b) Compaction rate SNTHERM due to metamorphism, the colour range is from -1.5 to 0 $\% \text{ h}^{-1}$. SNOWPACK is mainly dominated with red ($=0$ $\% \text{ h}^{-1}$) with only few blue parts. SNTHERM has a more evenly distributed green (around -0.7 $\% \text{ h}^{-1}$) near the surface and red more deeper in the snowpack.

Figure 6.9: (a) Sig/η SNOWPACK. ($\% \text{ h}^{-1}$), (b) Viscosity SNOWPACK (GPa s)

Figure 6.10: Modelled temperature in the snowpack. The arrows indicate a drop in temperature (just before sub snowfall I) and the relatively high temperature during sub snowfall II.

Chapter 7

Summary

In this project, verification data for the snowcover model SNOWPACK was obtained during the winter season 2005/2006 on the SLF study plot located at Weissfluhjoch, 2540 m a.s.l. near Davos, Switzerland. Valuable data was collected with resolutions in time and space that are unique. Apart from what has been done in this thesis, this data has great potential for future work. In this final Chapter, the results will be shortly summarised and discussed.

7.1 New snow microstructure

Three different periods in winter and spring were analysed. Approximately half the amount of the macrophotos was processed. Due to time constraints and developments in the imaging software, it was decided not to proceed with processing the photos and the iso-octane samples.

From the processed images, shape parameters such as dendricity and sphericity were determined. These parameters were compared to the meteorological conditions at the time of sample collection. The results showed a relationship between dendricity and windspeed. The dendricity decreased with increasing windspeed. Air temperature, snow surface temperature and relative humidity did not show any relationship with dendricity. Sphericity did not show any relation with meteorological parameters either.

The results showed that dendricity of new snow should not be treated as a constant value in SNOWPACK. However, before processing more macrophotos and building a parametrization for the dendricity, the sensitivity of SNOWPACK for a varying new snow dendricity should be thoroughly tested. In addition, the imaging software should be thoroughly tested to evaluate the different fitting procedures in order to obtain reliable results.

The large amount and high quality of collected crystals originating from different meteorological conditions have a big potential for future insights in crystal shapes and possible shape parameters. In addition, the comparison of the crystals collected on the snow surface and the crystals taken from the air with iso-octane samples can give insight into on-ground processes. However, the use of iso-octane is not as ideal as the in-situ photographing since the crystals are easily damaged during the drying process.

7.2 New snow density

Throughout the winter season 2005/2006, new snow densities were measured at a relatively high time resolution. The new snow densities were measured on a half hourly to hourly basis depending on the intensity of the snowfall. In total, 100 measurements were made. A new parametrisation is built based on these measurements. The new parametrisation has air temperature, wind speed and relative humidity as predictor variables. A striking feature in the measurements was a reversal towards higher densities below $-14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. An important step in the regression analysis was therefore the splitting of the temperature regime which led to a large increase in explained variance. Although the increase in new snow density for lower temperatures is

plausible according to the snow morphology diagram, the statistical basis for this effect is very weak since the amount of measurements in this range is small. More measurements in this temperature regime (below $-14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) are needed to investigate if this effect is always present. Until now, the parametrisation is discontinuous at $-14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Given the few measurements in this range, it is difficult to make realistic assumptions of parametrisation curves. Therefore, the discontinuous parametrisation will be used until more measurements can be made.

The new density parametrisation was tested on a older data set of 2001/2002. The results show that the new parametrisation performed better than the old parametrisation with correlation coefficients between predicted and measured new snow density of 0.56 and 0.18 for the new and old parametrisation respectively. The correlation coefficients for season 2005/2006 were -0.1 and 0.81 for the old and new parametrisation respectively. The difference between the two parametrisations are mainly due to the different range of measurements on which the two parametrisations were based. The old parametrisation was very limited, especially in the temperature range. The new parametrisation gives systematically higher new snow densities than the old parametrisation. The difference between the two datasets upon which the parametrisations are based not only lays in the different range of meteorological variables, but also the location at which is measured. The old measurements were mainly conducted in the village Davos at 1600 m and the new measurements were conducted on the Weissflujoch at 2540 m. Errors in measurements can occur due to a time delay in which the new snow settles already and density increases during the time of measurement. The measurements were made carefully and the precipitation intensity during time of measurement was taken into account, so this effect ought to be very small. Furthermore, the conditions during the measurements may be disturbed by the village Davos itself so that the measured meteorological variables are not representative for the measured new snow densities. The large variability between locations is a difficult point which is not fully understood. It is assumed that in the case of the automatic weather stations throughout the Alps, the measured meteorological variables determine the new snow density and that parameters such as altitude are not influencing the new snow density.

Although the new parametrisation results in a significant improvement in the prediction of new snow density, there is still one point that needs attention. It is assumed that the local conditions are related to new snow properties and when local meteorological conditions are known, parameters such as new snow density can be determined. However, new snow is formed by in-cloud processes. To fully understand and predict new snow properties, in-cloud information is needed. Till now, it is not logistically possible to obtain incloud information for all measurements stations. However, for future more precise predictions, high resolution weather models should be linked to new snow properties in order to make a more precise and reliable new snow property prediction.

7.3 Measured profiles

After three snowfall events, snow profiles were made. The SMP instrument was used to measure the hardness of the new snow layer. Until now, new snow layers were not investigated on such a small scale with the SMP. The resistance that the SMP measured was related to the snow density. In the few days after a snowfall event, a clear distinction was observed between the different times of measurement. In all cases, the resistance was linearly related to the measured density profile. Two phases were observed. First, a strong densification in which the resistance did not increase strongly with increasing density. Second, a phase in which the resistance increased strongly with little increase in density. The first phase was recognised as the phase in which only grain boundary diffusion took place. Water vapour is only transported locally and here is little bond growth. The second phase was recognised as the phase in which temperature gradients drive inter granular water vapour transport. Water vapour is transported over larger distances and there is stronger bond growth. In the first phase, densification was observed without large changes in mechanical properties (read change in resistance). On the contrary, in the second phase, the mechanical properties of the snowcover changes and the resistance increases strongly.

The observed change in mechanical properties can serve as a verification of SNOWPACK since this cor-

responds with a change of for example in crystal type. Although there is always spatial variability due to wind or radiation effects, the SMP is a promising tool for the verification of SNOWPACK.

7.4 Snowpack simulations

The new density parametrization was implemented in SNOWPACK and runs were made for season 2005/2006. A comparison was made between the performance of two SNOWPACK versions, with the old and new density parametrisation. Although SNOWPACK was tuned on the old density parametrisation, the mass predictions of the new model version were improved compared to the old version. In addition, a test run was made on season 1995/1996. For this season, the new model version showed a slight improvement in mass prediction as well.

A case study was conducted on a snowfall event in March. Measured density profiles were compared with the modelled density profiles of the new snow layer. Both the old and new model versions were in the correct range. However, the new model version showed more structure, partly quite similar to the measured density profile. Furthermore, measured settling curves were compared with modelled settling curves from both old- and new model versions. Both model versions showed approximately the same settling curves, this is explained by the way the snowdepth is prescribed. In general the model settled to slow, especially in the lower part of the snowpack. Since the initial conditions were assumed to be correct, the cause of the error was found in the settling descriptions.

A comparison was made with the settling description of the SN THERM model. The comparison showed that settling due to metamorphism is only shortly present in SNOWPACK compared to SN THERM. Furthermore, this mechanism of settling was only restricted to a small part close to the surface during sub snowfalls II and III. The settling due to overload in SNOWPACK was examined as well. The main problem was found to be that the old snow layer did not react quickly enough on the new snow on top of it. In the end, both the settling due to metamorphism and overload were hardly present in the old snowlayer during sub snowfall I. This is found to be the cause of the incorrectly modelled initial stage of the settling curves. A possible explanation might be the sudden drop in modelled temperature just before the start of sub snowfall I. The drop in temperature might increase the viscosity in such a way that settling is prevented.

Although the analysis mentioned above gave insight into the different possible errors, systematic and thorough sensitivity tests are needed to isolate the influence of the different parameters in the settling process. On the other hand, the overall performance of SNOWPACK is not bad, the results are in the correct range and the errors in the initial settling stage are in the order of around 5 cm. Overall we can conclude that this case study is reasonably well modelled.

Appendix A

NIR and Diethylphtalate samples

Figure A.1: Example of a NIR photograph. In a section of the profile, the contrast is enhanced and the stratigraphy of the profile becomes visible. After processing the image, parameters such as specific surface area of the different grains can be determined.

Figure A.2: Example of a photo of a processed diethylphthalate sample. The sample is cut in the cold laboratory and every slice is photographed.

Appendix B

Statistical techniques

In this appendix, a short description is given about the statistical techniques used. Additional information can be found in Stahel (2006).

A simple model for a linear regression between a target variable Y_i and predictor variables $x_i^{(1)}, x_i^{(2)}, \dots, x_i^{(m)}$ could be

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i^{(1)} + \beta_2 x_i^{(2)} + \dots + \beta_m x_i^{(m)} + E_i, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where β_0 is the intercept with the y axis, $\beta_{(1\dots m)}$ are the different coefficients for the predictor variables and E_i are the errors. Assumed is for the errors:

- The expectation value of E_i is $\epsilon \langle E_i \rangle = 0$,
- they have the same variance $\text{var} \langle E_i \rangle = \sigma^2$,
- they are normal distributed,
- they are independent.

Linear means that the model is linear in its coefficients, the predictor terms do not have to be linear. The coefficients $\beta_{(0\dots m)}$ and σ are the parameters of the model. These parameters are determined in such a way that the sum of the squared deviations is reduced to a minimum (least square fit).

The residuals are defined as the difference between the fitted values \hat{y}_i and target value Y_i ,

$$R_i = Y_i - \hat{y}_i, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

with

$$\hat{y}_i = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 x_i^{(1)} + \hat{\beta}_2 x_i^{(2)} + \dots + \hat{\beta}_m x_i^{(m)}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where $\hat{\beta}_{(0\dots m)}$ are the estimated coefficients. In order to find the optimal model, certain tests and plots are helpful. The parameters and tests used are listed in below: (for an example see table 5.2)

- *coef* Estimated coefficient.
- *stcoef* Standardized regression coefficient, this value gives a measure for the weight of the influence of the predictor variable on the target variable. Comparison can be made between the different coefficients.
- *signif* T-ratio, gives a measure for the level of significance, in cases where the p.value is zero and distinction in terms of significance is difficult. If *signf* is higher, a coefficient is more significant. For values of *signf* larger than 1, the coefficient is significant. $1/\text{signif}$).
- *R2.x* Gives a measure for the collinearity between the variables. This means, how strong the different terms are correlated to each other. If the collinearity is high between terms, the coefficients are poorly determined and there is not a unique solution.

- *p.value* Gives the probability for the occurrence of extremer values than the observed values. When the *p.value* is small enough (level often set to 0.05), then the influence of the term is significant, and not caused by chance.
- *St.dev.error* Standard deviation of E_i .
- R^2 Coefficient of determination, measure for the amount of variance explained by the predictor variables. It is the ratio regression variance over the total variance of the target value.
- *adjusted- R^2* As above, but corrected for the amount of predictor variables, because R^2 always increases with increasing amount of predictor variables. The adjusted- R^2 only increases when the new terms improve the model more then would be expected by chance.
- *F-statistic* Gives a measure for the overall performance of the model. it is the ratio of regression variance over the residual variance.

For a more detailed description of the different statistical tests and parameters referred is to the literature, Stahel (2006). The parameters listed above give a good representation of the performance of a model but with this numerical output it is difficult to see where possible improvements can be made. Therefore, the residuals are analyzed with the help of a graphical representation. The following plots are used:

- residuals against fitted values (Tukey-Anscombe plot).
- absolute standardized residuals against fitted values (abs(st.res(Y))-Fitted values). The absolute standardized values are shown instead of the residuals. This makes it more easy to examine how the residuals vary over the fitted values and if for example transformations (more on transformations in section 5.1.2) are necessary.
- normal distributed diagram (st.res(Y)-Theoretical Quantiles), gives the theoretical quantiles (normal distributed) and the empirical quantiles. If the residuals are distributed normally, the empirical quantiles should be on the line $y=x$.
- leverage plot (st.res(Y)-hat diagonal), gives insight on the influence of different outliers. The distance on the x-axis is the so called leverage distance. An outlier at the ends of the regression line (read large distance to pivot point) has a much larger influence on the regression line and should be treated with special care.
- scatter of residuals against each variable (Residuals-Predictor variable), with the help of these plots the influence of the different variables on the target variable can be examined individually.

The numbers in the plot itself (not the axes) represent outliers that are outside of the plotted domain. The thick dotted line (smooth) is the running mean of the residuals (along the fitted values), the thin dotted simulated curves represent a relatively simple graphical test to examine the model performance and are obtained in the following way:

1. For a number of simulations n , standard-normalized distributed random errors E_i^* are produced.
2. With E_i^* , new values for Y_i^* are determined according to $Y_i^* = \hat{y} + \hat{\sigma} E_i^*$.
3. A regression analysis is done for the new Y_i against the variables in the dataset. The running mean is computed again and showed in the Tukey-Anscombe plot.

If the simulated curves look more 'extreme' than the measured curve, the error is significant and not a coincidence. In this case, there is an error in the model that should be eliminated. In comparison with the 5% tests, Davies (1995) recommended 19 simulations. An informal graphical test would than consist of having the 20 curves examined by objective people and asking them point out the most 'extreme' curve. If this is the curve that corresponds to the measurements, the error is significant.

For an ideal model, the smooth would be on the green reference line $R_i=0$. The dotted blue line is the reference line for constant value of the measured target value Y_i . The line helps to examine the influences of the different predictor variables on the target variable individually.

Appendix C

Used meteo instruments

Two measurement frames were used to record the meteorological parameters: (i)MST (set up where harps were placed, 1.5m above snow) and (ii)METE (4m above snow, 10m horizontal distance of MST). The instruments on the METE station were ventilated and therefore had the preference to use in the data analyzing. However, the disadvantage is that these instruments were not directly at the position where the harps were placed and manual measurements were taken.

The Figure C.1(a) and C.1(b) were measurements during a snowfall which took place in the period 08.03-09.03 and the Figures C.1(c) and C.1(d) are from a period where the weather was good. The Figures show that during a snowfall both instruments (ventilated/non-ventilated) give approximately the same values for the temperature, errors in the order of 1 °C. For the humidity, the error can go up to 30 percent. The ventilated sensor was reacting quicker on changing air temperatures, the drop in humidity in Figure C.1(b) took place earlier then the drop in the non-ventilated instrument, which needed a longer adjustment time. On the contrary Figure C.1(c) shows a large difference between the two instruments. During the day when the instrument absorbed radiation, the non-ventilated instrument gives much higher values than the ventilated instrument. The quicker respond time and lower dependancy of radiation validates the decision of using the ventilated IMIS instruments for air temperature and humidity although they are not directly at the position where the harps were positioned and the manual measurements were taken. The further analysis and model runs were done with the data from the METE ventilated instruments, unless stated otherwise.

Figure C.1: Temperature and relative humidity plots. (a,b) during snowfall and (c,d) during good a weather period.

References

- Bartelt, P. and Lehning, M. (2002). A physical snowpack model for the swiss avalanche warning. part i: numerical model. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 35:123–145.
- Bossolasco, M. (1954). New fallen snow and air temperature. *Nature*, 174:362–363.
- Brun, E., Martin, E., Simon, V., Gendre, C., and C. (1989). An energy and mass model of snow cover suitable for operational avalanche forecasting. *J. Glaciol.*, 35:333–342.
- Brun, E., P.David, Sudul, M., and Brunot, G. (1992). A numerical model to simulate snow-cover stratigraphy for operational avalanche forecasting. *J.Glaciol.*, 38:13–22.
- Colbeck, S., Akitaya, E., Armostrong, R., Gubler, H., Lafeuille, J., Lied, K., McClung, D., and Morris, E. (1991). The international classification for seasonal snow on the ground. *International Commission on Snow and Ice*.
- Davies, P. (1995). Data features. *Statistica Neerlandica*, 49:185–245.
- Diamond, M. and Lowry, W. (1954). Correlation of density of new snow with 700- millibar temperature. *Journal of Meteorology*, 11:512–513.
- Gold, L. W. and Power, B. A. (1954). Dependence of the forms of natural snow crystals on meteorological conditions. *Journal of Meteorology*, 11:35–42.
- Grant, L. and Rhea, J. (1974). Elevation and meteorological controls on the density of snow. *Adv. Concepts Tech. Study Snow Ice Resource. Interdisciplinary Symp.*, pages 169–181.
- Gray et al. 1979 (1979). ‘Snow accumulation and distribution’, in Colbeck, S. C. and Ray, M. (eds), *Proceedings of Modelling Snow*. Cover Runo?, US Army Cold Regions Research Laboratory, Hanover.
- Hendrikx, J. (2002). Microstructural parameters of new snow as a function of meteorological conditions. Interim-ship report SLF.
- Jamieson (1997). *The compression test for snow stability. Proceedings of the October 1996 International Snow Science Workshop in Banff*. Canadian Avalanche Association, Revelstoke, BC, Canada.
- Jordan, R. (1991). A one-dimensional temperature model for a snowcover: Technical documentation for sntherm.89. *Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, Hanover, N.H., 1991.*, Technical Report CRREL Special Report 91-16.
- Judson, A. and Doesken, N. (2000). Density of freshly fallen snow in the central rocky mountains. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 81:1577–1587.
- Kajikawa, M., N.Sato, Y.Asuma, and Kikuchi, K. (2006). Characteristics of new snow density and compressive viscosity in the arctic region. *Journal of the Japanese Society of Snow & Ice*, 68(4):277–285.
- Lehning, M., Bartelt, P., Brown, B., and Fierz, C. (2002a). A physical snowpack model for the swiss avalanche warning. part iii: meteorological forcing, thin layer formation and evaluation. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 35:169–184.

- Lehning, M., Bartelt, P., Brown, B., Fierz, C., and Satyawali, P. (2002b). A physical snowpack model for the swiss avalanche warning. part ii: Snow microstructure. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 35:147–167.
- Lesaffre, B., Pougatch, E., and Martin, E. (1998). Objective determination of snow-grain characteristics from images. *International Glaciological Society*.
- Libbrecht, K. (2005). The physics of snow crystals. *Rep. Prog. Phys.*, 68:855895.
- Lütschg, M., Bartelt, P., Lehning, M., Stoeckli, V., and Haeberli, W. (2003). Numerical simulation of the interaction processes between snowcover and alpine permafrost. *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Permafrost, 21-25 July, Zurich, Switzerland*.
- Matzl, M. and Schneebeli, M. (2002). Stratigraphy of snow profiles using near-infrared photography. *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, pages B992+.
- McGurk, B., Azuma, D., and Kattelman, R. (1988). Density of new snow in the central sierra nevada. Proc. 56th Annual Meeting, Kalispell, MT, Western Snow Conference 158-161.
- Meirolid-Mautner, I. and Lehning, M. (2003). Measurement and modeling of the solar shortwave fluxes in snow on summit/greenland. *Ann. of Glaciol.* in press.
- Meister, R. (1985). Density of new snow and its dependance on air temperature and wind. *Workshop on the correction of Precipitation Measurements*.
- Painter, T., Molotch, N., Cassidy, M., Flanner, M., and Steffen, K. (2007). Contact spectroscopy for determination of stratigraphy of snow optical grain size. *Journal of Glaciology*, 53(180):121–127.
- Perret, F. (2000). New snow dendricity as a function of meteorological parameters. Interim-ship report SLF.
- Rasmus, S., J.Räisänen, and Lehning, M. (2003). Estimate snow conditions in finland in the late 21st century using the snowpack-model with regional climate scenario data as input. *Ann. of Glaciol.* in press.
- Roebber, P., Bruening, S., Schultz, D., and Cortinas, J. (2002). Improving snowfall forecasting by diagnosing snow density. *American Meteorological Society*, 18:264–286.
- Schneebeli, M., Pielmeier, C., and Johnson, J. (1999). Measuring snow microstructure and hardness using a high resolution penetrometer. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 30:101–114.
- Stahel, W. (2006). Lineare regression. *Seminar fur Statistik ETH Zurich*. <http://stat.ethz.ch/~stahel/courses/regression/>.
- Wetzel, M., Meyers, M., Borys, R., Mcanelly, R., W.Cotton, A.Rossi, D.Nadler, P., D.Lowenthal, S.Cohn, and W.Brown (2004). Mesoscale snowfall prediction and verification in mountainous terrain. *Weather and Forecasting*, 19:806–828.